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RIGOUROUS -

secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 5.1

**PLATFORM PROTOTYPE INTEGRATION AND
IN-LAB TESTING**

Title	Platform Prototype Integration and In-lab testing
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/Definition
5GS	5G System
5GTN	OULU's 5G Test Network
6GS	6G System
AAE	Adversarial Autoencoder
ACK	Acknowledgment
AE	Autoencoder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AID	AI-driven Decision
AKMA	Authentication and Key Management for Applications
B5G	5G and beyond
BEST	Battery Efficient Security for very low throughput Machine Type Communication (MTC) devices
CAE	Convolutional Autoencoder
CDOM	Cognitive Decision, Orchestration, and Management
CDP	Cisco Discovery Protocol
CITEF	Cyber Integration, Test and Evaluation Framework
CL	Continual Learning
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CTI	Cyber Threat Information
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DevSecOps	Development, Security, and Operations
DL	Deep Learning
DM	Data Monitoring
DoS	Denial of Service
DP	Differential Privacy
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DS	Data Services
DSC	Dynamic and automated Service Composition
DT	Digital Twins
E2E	End-to-End
EaaS	Encryption-as-a-Service
EAP	Extensible Authentication Protocol
EDoS	Economical Denial of Sustainability
FED AI	Federated AI Anomaly Detection
FL	Federated Learning

GAT	Graph Attention
GBA	General Bootstrapping Architecture
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HLA	High-Level Architecture
HSPF	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IIoT	Industrial IoT
IoT	Internet of Things
IoT SP	IoT Service Provider
IT/OT	Information and Operation Technology
LLDP	Link-Layer Discovery Protocol
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MISP	Threat Intelligence Sharing Platform
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSE	Mean Square Error
MSPL	Medium-Level Security Policy Language
MTC	Machine Type Communication
MTD	Moving Target Defense
MTD	Moving Target Defense
NAI	Network Access Identifier
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
NPN	Non-Public Network
NSFM	Network Security Flow Monitoring
OAM	Operations, Administration, and Management
PC	Physical Correlator
PETs	Privacy Enhancing Technologies
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer

RM	Response Mitigation
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SAE	Security Analytics Engine
SaaS	Software as a Service
SCA	Slicing Control Agent
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMPS	Slicing Mitigation Planner Service
SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol
SO	Security Orchestrator
SOAR	Security, Orchestration, Administration, and Response
SSLA	Security Service Level Agreement
SUCI	Subscription Concealed Identifier
TEDP	Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol
TEFS	Trust Evaluation and enabler Service Function
TIA	Topology Inventory Agent
TIP	Threat Intelligence Platform
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
TTP	Tactics, Technics, and Procedures
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UE	User Equipment
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
vCDN	virtual Content Delivery Network
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VXLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
WMI	Windows Management Instrumentation
WPS	Wi-Fi Protected Setup
ZTM	Zero Trust Model
ZTS	Zero Trust Security

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents Deliverable 5.1 “Platform Prototype Integration and In-lab Testing,” and focus on the Integration Plan.

Considering the challenges linked to any integration activity, this document presents the steps required towards achieving a fully functional RIGOUROUS architecture. Part of this process encompasses the identification of the integrations required between the different RIGOUROUS Assets, Testbeds and UCs, which has been achieved and is presented in this document.

Furthermore, a two-stage prototype approach is planned for this project, in line with the project MS5 “Initial version of application enablers and software modules” and MS7 “Final RIGOUROUS enablers and framework”. Thus, all the integration activities have been carefully planned to fulfil this objective.

1 INTRODUCTION

This document aims to report on the integration plans of the RIGOUROUS project.

The diversity of Assets, UCs and Testbeds that compose the RIGOUROUS ecosystem, requires a proper integration planning, testing and validation. Given the ongoing developments under WP2, WP3, and WP4, mainly focusing on the development of individual Assets or UCs, proper integration plans are crucial. Collaborative efforts across these work packages will lead to two working prototypes, in line with the project MS5 and MS7.

This deliverable outlines the defined integration and evaluation activities, detailing the steps required to achieve a functional RIGOUROUS framework. WP5 activities are structured to yield preliminary results early on, providing feedback to other WPs. A two-stage incremental approach is adopted to enable the earliest identification of potential issues with the RIGOUROUS framework, providing time to overcome them, thus, contributing to an enhanced framework. Such two-cycle process is evident in most of the WP5 tasks.

The remaining of this document is structured as follows: Section 2 details the overall Integration Plan, by presenting the Integration Methodology, the Roadmap Overview, the used Common Tools and the Interfaces Template. Section 3 presents the Integration Strategy, Asset and UC Mapping by detailing the mapping of Functional Blocks of the RIGOUROUS architecture to the list of Assets, the integration points and list of interfaces, the mapping between Assets to UCs, Testbeds and Roadmap and lastly the mapping of UCs to Testbeds and Roadmap. Section 4 presents the InLab Testing activities. Section 5 presents the conclusions of this deliverable. This document also contains four annexes: (i) Annex I: Assets Template, which presents the Asset template; (ii) Annex II: UCs Template, which contains the UCs template; (iii) Annex III: Testbeds Template, which presents the testbeds template; and (iv) Annex IV: Interfaces Definition, which presents the definition of the interfaces according to the Interfaces template.

2 INTEGRATION PLAN

This section details the integration plans to achieve a unified and assessed version of the RIGUROUS framework. In fact, components developed in different WPs (WP2-4) will have to be integrated and validated, to form a working version of the project framework.

The complexity is the primary challenge when dealing with the integration between such a vast set of architectural layers and respective components, while aiming to achieve a prototype. It is essential to acknowledge from an early stage that numerous partners with diverse backgrounds and experiences from distinct domains (institutional institutions, SMEs, etc) need to collaborate to develop and integrate their work into a unified prototype. The elevated number of components and interactions adds an additional layer of complexity, making the initial integrated prototype crucial for validating the project architecture and respective interactions. To address the complexity inherent in developing the unified prototype, a detailed integration work plan is outlined in the subsequent sub-sections.

The integration process is divided into two major phases, each having specific requirements to be fulfilled by the Asset, UC and testbed owners. The initial phase aims to generate a preliminary, functional prototype of the RIGUROUS architecture, with an “Initial Version of application enablers and software modules” (MS5). This prototype will encompass essential features of the project architecture, namely the operability between its different Functional Blocks. During the first phase, the testbeds are actively supporting deployment and integration efforts for selected Assets and UCs, while facilitating validation and experimentation concurrently.

The second phase, corresponding to the second stage prototype, will correspond to the “Final RIGUROUS enablers and framework” (MS7), where all the integrations have been completed and assessed and the framework will be ready for demonstration activities and, later on, for open-source reference implementation.

The foreseen integrations and demonstrations aim to validate the project’s KPIs as defined in the RIGUROUS DoW. The correlation between each integration and the project KPIs is described throughout Sections 3.3 and 3.4, with all the integration tables presenting a dedicated row to this end.

This section is organized as follows: Methodology (Section 2.1), Roadmap (Section 2.2) and Common Tools (Section 2.3).

2.1. Methodology

Considering the high number of components evolved in the RIGUROUS architecture, a detailed integration plan has been defined to prevent any potential unseen and unwanted occurrences in the integration process.

The suggested integration methodology was carefully designed considering the challenges posed by the project architecture and builds upon the following objectives:

- Definition of an integration plan and methodology: Design of the Integration Plan, including the definition of iterative and collaborative procedures to ensure effective planning, coordination, monitoring and assessment of the integration process.
- Identification of all involved components: Clarifying components, including their functionality, responsibilities and characteristics.
- Specification of the interfaces and involved components: Defining interfaces, standardizing message formats, and establishing protocols.
- Design of functional tests and KPIs: Establishing a comprehensive set of tests and indicators to evaluate and measure the success of each integration and individual contribution towards the project goals.
- Definition of the integration, experimentation, and demonstration environments: Defining the different environments used for integration, experimentation, and demonstration activities with a focus on distributed mock-up enablers on-premises testbeds.

Figure 1 - Integration Methodology.

The Integration Methodology, depicted in Figure 1, considers several steps, which are developed throughout the different WP5 tasks and culminate with one of the three WP5 deliverables: D5.1 (Platform Prototype Integration and In-lab testing, due by M18), D5.2 (Platform Prototype Integration and In-lab testing, due by M24) or D5.3 (In-lab testing, validation and evaluation and showcasing, due by M36). A brief description of each step is provided hereafter:

- **Integration Plan (M06-M12)**: This phase includes the definition of the technical integration plan. In addition, the activities of WP2, WP3 and WP4 were closely monitored to infer the relative information for the integration activities.

- Roadmap (M07-M14): This phase includes the definition of a thorough experimentation roadmap, which considers the project milestones and guides the integrations activities aiming to achieve them.
- Evaluation Plan (M12-M18): This phase includes the definition of specific KPIs aiming to assess and validate the conducted integrations, enabling its proper monitoring.
- First Prototype Integration (M11-M18): This phase includes the integration activities required towards the achievement of the first prototype integration, in line with the project MS5 (Initial version of application enablers and software modules).
- Second Prototype Integration (M18-M30): This phase includes the integration activities required towards the achievement of the second prototype, in line with the project MS7 (Final RIGOUROUS enablers and framework)
- InLab testing (M18-M36): This phase includes all the integration activities linked with testing and validation activities conducted in the RIGOUROUS testbeds, namely between different RIGOUROUS Assets and UCs, thus actively contributing to the second prototype.
- Validation and evaluation (M24-M36): This phase includes the definition of specific scenarios under which the different components will be assessed. It also involves designing demonstration scenarios to showcase the RIGOUROUS framework.
- Showcase (M24-M36): This phase includes the showcase activities aiming to disseminate the RIGOUROUS architecture, namely its functional blocks and UCs.

2.2. Roadmap Overview

Figure 2 presents the Integration Roadmap, which includes a set of integration milestones that were defined to better guide the different integration activities, bearing in mind the project milestones and two-stage prototype approach.

Figure 2 - Integration Roadmap.

Table 1 describes each of the integration plan milestones (IP-MS), thus providing explanatory information over the different steps identified in Figure 2.

Table 1 - Integration Milestones.

Milestone	Month	Description	Achieved Goals
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IP-MS1	M13	Initial version of the Integration Plan and Methodology has been defined. In addition, the mapping between UCs and Testbeds, as well as, the mapping between Assets and Testbeds have been achieved.	Integration Plan and Methodology
IP-MS2	M14	Definition of the interfaces to be used among the different Assets/Functional Blocks as part of the normal behaviour of the RIGOUROUS architecture.	Interfaces Definition
IP-MS3	M15	Preliminary deployment of the UCs and Assets at the selected testbeds (every asset and UC must have completed, at least, one preliminary deployment)	Testbed Integration
IP-MS4 MS4	M16	Successful integration between enablers and testbeds, including collection of preliminary KPIs.	Mockup Enablers running on the testbed
IP-MS5	M17	Preliminary integration between Assets and UCs (all the UCs must have completed, at least, one integration with the selected Assets)	Assets-UCs Integration
IP-MS6 MS5	M18	Successful integration between Assets and UCs, including collection of preliminary KPIs.	Initial version of application enablers and software modules
First Phase			
IP-MS7	M20	Preliminary integration between cross-layer functional blocks.	Cross-Layer Integration
IP-MS8	M22	Successful integration between cross-layer functional blocks, enabling the validation of the actions defined by the Proactive and Reactive approaches. Collection of preliminary KPIs.	Proactive & Reactive architecture validation
Second Phase			
IP-MS9 MS6	M24	Validation and assessment of the RIGOUROUS framework.	In-Lab RIGOUROUS integrated framework assessment
IP-MS10	M27	Design and validation of the demonstration scenarios focused on demonstrating the multiple aspects of the RIGOUROUS framework.	Demonstration Scenarios
IP-MS11 MS7	M30	Final version of all the RIGOUROUS components. All the integrations must have been closed at this time and the	Final RIGOUROUS enablers and framework

		entire platform should be ready for demonstration activities.	
IP-MS12	M33	Several demonstrations must have been achieved at this time, showcasing the RIGOUROUS Assets and UCs. For each demonstration, KPIs must have been collected.	Show-cases & evaluation
IP-MS13 MS8	M36	Assessment and dissemination of all the demonstration activities and open-source release of some RIGOUROUS components	Final case study assessment and open-source reference implementation

2.3. Common Tools

Two common tools have been installed and made available to the RIGOUROUS partners, aiming to expedite the RIGOUROUS activities: OnlyOffice and Gitlab. These tools are briefly described in the following sub-sections.

2.3.1. ONLYOFFICE

ONLYOFFICE [1] is a comprehensive office productivity suite that includes a range of tools for document creation, management, and collaboration. This tool is an office-like collaboration suite that can be used as a Software as a Service (SaaS) solution or as a private installation on partners premises and it has been selected as the repository to be used in RIGOUROUS, namely for file management.

Figure 3 – RIGOUROUS ONLYOFFICE.

The most relevant features of ONLYOFFICE are:

- **Comprehensive Toolset:** ONLYOFFICE integrates a variety of office productivity tools into one platform, including word processing, spreadsheets, presentations, project management, CRM, and email.
- **Cross-Platform Support:** ONLYOFFICE is available on various operating systems (Windows, MacOS, Linux) and can be accessed through web browsers.
- **Collaboration Features:** The platform supports real-time co-editing, commenting, and version control.
- **Customization:** ONLYOFFICE offers extensive customization options, including the ability to integrate third-party applications and use its API for tailored solutions.
- **Security:** The platform includes robust security features such as data encryption, access controls, and compliance with industry standards.
- **Integration Capabilities:** ONLYOFFICE can be integrated with other popular services such as Nextcloud, ownCloud, Confluence, and SharePoint.
- **Document Management:** Provides features for storing, managing, and sharing documents securely.
- **Mobile Accessibility:** ONLYOFFICE offers mobile apps for both iOS and Android devices.
- **Support for Multiple File Formats:** The platform supports a wide range of file formats including DOCX, XLSX, PPTX, and ODF and allows online edition.

2.3.2. Gitlab

GitLab [2] offers source code management, verification, accessibility, and security, along with other features crucial for a Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) workflow. It has been chosen as the DevOps platform to use. A GitLab instance is available at [HTTPS://GITLAB.RIGOUROUS.EU](https://gitlab.rigorous.eu), with access granted to all consortium partners.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL https://gitlab.rigorous.eu/users/sign_in. The page features the GitLab logo (a stylized fox head) and the text "GitLab Community Edition". Below this is a sign-in form with two input fields: "Username or primary email" and "Password". The "Password" field has a toggle for visibility. To the right of the password field is a link that says "Forgot your password?". Below the input fields is a checkbox labeled "Remember me" and a blue "Sign in" button. At the bottom of the form area, there is a link that says "Don't have an account yet? Register now".

Figure 4 – RIGOUROUS Gitlab.

- **Git Source Code Management:** GitLab serves as a centralized repository and management system for the RIGOUROUS source code. Utilizing Git as a distributed version control system,

developers can clone the code to a local machine, providing a safe environment for experimentation without impacting the overall system functionality. Once changes or new features are implemented, the updated code is pushed back to the remote repository, making it accessible to the entire development team. This setup allows multiple developers to work on the same codebase without interference, minimizing the effort needed to resolve merge conflicts.

- **GitLab CI/CD:** GitLab includes tools for continuous software development, enabling immediate building and testing of the software as soon as a developer commits a file to the repository (CI), and providing a production-ready build of the CI-validated code at any time (CD).
- **GitLab Container Registry:** GitLab offers a private registry for images, which include everything necessary to run an application, such as source code and dependencies. This feature allows developers to build, push, and deploy Docker containers using GitLab CI, facilitating application testing whenever changes are made to branches or tags. For proprietary code, partners will provide a README file detailing the component's functionality and the provisioned API, with each partner responsible for manually updating the Container Registry.
- **Kubernetes Integration:** GitLab integrates with Kubernetes (K8s) in several ways, most notably by enabling the build and deployment of software from GitLab CI/CD pipelines to a K8s cluster, which is crucial for the RIGOUROUS Integration Plan.
- **GitLab Wiki:** The GitLab Wiki tool is used for project documentation. While anyone can view wiki pages, only designated developers can create and edit their content.

2.4. Interfaces Template

Following the good practices of an integration plan, an interface template has been defined so all the RIGOUROUS interfaces could be defined following the same pattern. Table 2 presents this template.

Table 2 - Interfaces template.

Field	Description
Interface code	Unique identifier of the interface
Status	design development testing validation completed
Component #1	Component name
Component #2	Component name
Direction	#1 to #2 #2 to #1
Description	A short description for the interface
Mode	Synchronous/Asynchronous
Standards/Protocols	e.g., REST, UDP, TCP, HTTP, RPC, etc
Format	e.g., JSON, YAML, XML, etc

Endpoint	e.g., api/endpoint
Operation	e.g., GET, POST, publish, subscribe
Request/Data Schema	Schema of the request/data
Request/Data Example	Example request/data
Response Schema	Schema of the response (optional)
Response Example	Example response data (optional)
Impact on #Component 1	A short description for the impact on #Component 1 (optional)
Impact on #Component 2	A short description for the impact on #Component 2 (optional)

3 INTEGRATION STRATEGY, ASSET AND UC MAPPING

This section delves into the integration strategy for the RIGOUROUS project, namely by presenting the mapping of Functional Blocks to Assets (Section 3.1), the integration points and list of interfaces (Section 3.2), the mapping of Assets to UCs, Testbeds and Roadmap – including the description of each integration, deployment and respective roadmap (Section 3.3), the mapping of UCs to Testbeds and Roadmap – including the description of each deployment and correspondent roadmap (Section 0).

3.1. Mapping of Functional Blocks to Assets

Figure 5 presents the mapping between RIGOUROUS Functional Blocks and the project Assets.

Figure 5 - Mapping of Functional Blocks to Assets.

Table 3 lists the RIGOUROUS Assets, including the corresponding RIGOUROUS Functional Blocks (when applicable). Although the majority of Assets map to Functional Blocks, some are provided exclusively in the form of specification, leading the RIGOUROUS ecosystem to apply and comply with the defined standardization practices and rules and allowing it to contribute to them.

Table 3 - List of RIGOUROUS's Assets.

#	Partner	Task	Assets	Functional Block
R02	UMU		Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification	Intent-Based Security

				Management (ISM)
R03	ITAV	3.1	Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps	NA
R04	ITAV	3.1	Onboarding tools	App Onboarding specification (AOUI)
R05	LNVO	3.1	Decentralized services based Identity and Trust management specification	NA
R07	UMU	3.2	AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments	Security Orchestrator (SO)
R08	LNVO	3.3	Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification	NA
R09	LNVO	3.2	IoT bootstrapping specification	NA
R10	LNVO	3.2	Trusted application onboarding specification	NA
R11	UWS	3.4	Slice manager	Slice Manager (SM)
R11	UWS	3.4	Network Self-Protection	SOAR
R12	ONE	4.1	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	Privacy Preserving Federated AI anomaly detection
R12	OULU	4.1	Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	Privacy Preserving Federated AI anomaly detection
R12	UMU	4.1	Privacy-preserving Federated AI for anomaly detection	Privacy Preserving Federated AI anomaly detection
R13	OULU	4.1	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator	NA
R14	OULU	4.1	MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)	MTD-based Robust AI
R15	WINGS	4.2	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition (DSC)
R15	WINGS	4.2	Digital Twin	Security Testing – Digital Twins (DT)
R16	eBOS	4.3	AI-driven decision making	Decision (AID)
R16	eBOS	4.4	AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision (6G AI RM)	Response Mitigation (RM)
R18	WINGS	4.3	Cyber Physical Correlator	AI-driven Cyber Physical Correlator
R19	RHEA	4.3	Threat Risk assessor (TRA)	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)
R20	UWS	4.4	Network Security Flow Monitoring	SOAR

R20	UWS	4.4	SOAR solution: Resource Inventory Agent, Security Detection Tool, Security Planner	SOAR
R21	ICTFI	4.4	Encryption as a Service	NA
R22	ITAV	3.1	Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management	NA
R23	UMU	4.1	Privacy-preserving CTI sharing	Privacy preserving CTI Sharing (CTI)

3.2. Integrations points and list of interfaces

Table 4 presents the latest list of the RIGOROUS interfaces. Several interfaces have already been defined following the interfaces template present in Section 2.4 and their definition is present in Annex IV: Interfaces Definition.

Table 4 - List of Interfaces.

Component #1	Component #2	Interface abbreviation	Development Status
Onboarding Tools (OT)	(PUI)	OT-PUI	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	(AOUI)	OT-AOUI	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	(SCUI)	OT-SCUI	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	(WEB_UI)	OT-WEB_UI	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	Security Orchestrator (SO)	OT-SO	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	Intent-Based Security Manager (ISM)	OT-ISM	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)	OT-TRA	Design
Onboarding Tools (OT)	(PQ)	OT-PQ	Design
Security Orchestrator (SO)	Intent-Based Security Manager (ISM)	SO-ISM	Development
Security Orchestrator (SO)	(NFV_MANO)	SO-NFV_MANO	Design
Security Orchestrator (SO)	Security Agent (SA)	SO-SA	Development
Security Orchestrator (SO)	Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification (TESF)	SO-TESF	Development
Security Orchestrator (SO)	Slice Manager (SM)	SO-SM	Design
Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification (TESF)	Slice Manager (SM)	TESF-SM	Design
Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification (TESF)	AI-driven decision making (AID)	TESF-AID	Design
Slice Manager (SM)	(NSP) [TBC]	SM-NSP	Design
R12 [ONE] Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF)	MTD-based Robust ML Models (MTD)	HSPF-MTD	Development
R12 [OULU] Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	Encryption as a Service (EaaS)	PPFLAD-EaaS	Development

AI-driven decision making (AID)	R12 [OULU] Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	AID-PPFLAD	Development
AI-driven decision making (AID)	R12 [UMU] Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	AID-PPFAIAD	Development
AI-driven decision making (AID)	R12 [ONE] Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF)	AID-HSPF	Development
AI-driven decision making (AID)	Cyber Physical Correlator (CPC)	AID-CPC	Development
AI-driven decision making (AID)	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)	AID-TRA	Design
AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision (AI RM)	Security Orchestrator (SO)	AI_RM-SO	Design
Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM)	Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	NSFM-SMPS	Design
Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	Topology Inventory Agent (TIA)	SMPS-TIA	Design
Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	Security Orchestrator (SO)	SMPS-SO	Design
Topology Inventory Agent (TIA)	Service Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS)	TIA-SMPS	Design
Topology Inventory Agent (TIA)	Slice Manager (SM)	TIA-SM	Design
AI-powered EDoS Mitigator (EDoS_M)	Data Monitoring (DM)	EDoS_DM	Development
AI-powered EDoS Mitigator (EDoS_M)	Admission Controller (AC)	EDoS_M-AC	Development
Encryption as a Service (EaaS)	R12 [OULU] Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	EaaS- PPFLAD	Design
Network-based MTD modeling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management (NMTD)	Security Orchestrator (SO)	NMTD-SO	Design
Network-based MTD modeling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management (NMTD)	Intent-Based Security Manager (ISM)	NMTD-ISM	Design
Network-based MTD modeling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management (NMTD)	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)	NMTD-TRA	Design

3.3. Mapping of Assets to UCs, Testbeds and Roadmap

This section presents the mapping of Assets to UCs and the mapping of Assets to Testbeds. Furthermore, this section encompasses several sub-sections that details each integration between Assets and UCs, Testbeds and presents its correspondent roadmap.

Table 5 presents the mapping of Assets to UCs.

Table 5 – Mapping of Assets to UCs.

#	Partner	Assets	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4
R02	UMU	Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification	x			
R03	ITAV	Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps				x
R04	ITAV	Onboarding tools				x
R05	LNVO	Decentralized services based Identity and Trust management specification	x		x	
R07	UMU	AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments	x			x
R08	LNVO	Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification	x			
R09	LNVO	IoT bootstrapping specification		x	x	x
R10	LNVO	Trusted application onboarding specification			x	x
R11	UWS	Slice manager	x			
R11	UWS	Network Self-Protection	x			
R12	ONE	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework				x
R12	OULU	Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector		x		
R12	UMU	Privacy-preserving Federated AI for anomaly detection				x
R13	OULU	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator		x		
R14	OULU	MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)				x
R15	WINGS	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition			x	
R15	WINGS	Digital Twin			x	
R16	eBOS	AI-driven decision making	x	x	x	x
R16	eBOS	AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision (6G AI RM)	x	x	x	x
R18	WINGS	Cyber Physical Correlator			x	
R19	RHEA	Threat Risk assessor (TRA)	x		x	x
R20	UWS	Network Security Flow Monitoring	x			
R20	UWS	SOAR solution: Resource Inventory Agent, Security Detection Tool, Security Planner	x			
R21	ICTFI	Encryption as a Service				x
R22	ITAV	Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management				x
R23	UMU	Privacy-preserving CTI sharing	x			

Table 6 presents the mapping of Assets to Testbeds.

Table 6 – Mapping of Assets to Testbeds.

#	Assets	UMU	ORO	EBO S	WINGS	OULU	ONE	ICTFI
R02	Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification	x						
R03	Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps						x	
R04	Onboarding tools						x	
R05	Decentralized services based Identity and Trust management specification							
R07	AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments		x				x	
R08	Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification							
R09	IoT bootstrapping specification						x	
R10	Trusted application onboarding specification							
R11	Slice manager		x					
R11	Network Self-Protection		x					
R12	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	x					x	
R12	Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector							x
R12	Privacy-preserving Federated AI for anomaly detection	x					x	
R13	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator					x		x
R14	MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)					x		
R15	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition				x			
R15	Digital Twin				x			
R16	AI-driven decision making		x	x	x		x	x
R16	AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision (6G AI RM)		x	x	x		x	x
R18	Cyber Physical Correlator				x			
R19	Threat Risk assessor		x	x	x		x	x
R20	Network Security Flow Monitoring		x					
R20	SOAR solution: Resource Inventory Agent, Security Detection Tool, Security Planner		x					
R21	Encryption as a Service							x

R22	Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management							x	
R23	Privacy-preserving CTI sharing	x	x						

3.3.1. R02: Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification

Table 7 presents the integration details between the Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification asset and UC1.

Table 7 - Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1
Integration description	6G requires a significant transformation of networks, shifting from dedicated network functions to software-based ones, deploying new physical infrastructure, and embracing network virtualization concepts and new 6G functions. This transition may introduce various security issues, spanning from physical infrastructure—Physical Network Functions (PNFs)—to virtualized infrastructure and implementations—Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). Additionally, 6G network functions (Service Based Architecture), 6G Management and Orchestration (MANO), as well as the control and data planes, could all be vulnerable to numerous cyber security attacks.
Integration objectives	Translate the MSPL security policies for securing external components.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-5: Increased accuracy in orchestration. KPI-8: Number of AI Algorithms devised for 6G orchestration >3.
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.

Table 8 details the testbed deployment of the Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification Asset at the UMU testbed.

Table 8 - Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	UMU Testbed

Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Translate a MSPL policy into a specific configuration message for a resource.
Goals	Transform abstract Protection Level and Security Level requirements into specific parameters for AI-driven Security Orchestrators. It provides a framework for defining Security Service Level Agreements (SSLAs), refines them into deployment-ready representations, enforces them in real time, and enables conflict detection.
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-6: AI-powered Orchestration of four (04) kinds of resources, namely: services, devices, virtual network functions, and physical network functions
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.

Table 9 details the roadmap for the Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification asset.

Table 9 - Intent-based Security & Privacy formal modelling and onboarding specification: Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
First prototype, being able to translate the configuration for initial MSPL policies	M16	T3.2
Updated prototype, with adjustments for new MSPL policies	M20	T3.2
Second prototype	Month	Task
Advanced version of the ISM, being able to process and generate more translations and more efficiently.	M25	3.2

3.3.2. R03: Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps

Table 10 presents the integration details between the Human-centric privacy risk management for DevSecOps asset and UC4.

Table 10 - Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	In the case of a PPDR event, it is necessary to handle many types of personal data swiftly and efficiently (for rapid response). Still, this data should not persist untreated beyond the PPDR event.
Integration objectives	The asset herein will discriminate and score the personal data handled during the PPDR event, allowing the understanding of how each data must be managed for persistent records.

Specific KPIs/KVIs	The asset will be explicitly evaluated on its capacity to discriminate flows with PII and correctly score them according to the normative framework (i.e., laws and best practices) in the jurisdiction of that deployment.
Risks	R1 – Inadequate management R2 – Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication R3 – Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase R5 – Deviations affecting schedule or budget R6 – A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic R7 – Gaps between needs and developed technology

Table 11 details the testbed deployment of the Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps asset at ONE’s testbed.

Table 11 - Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	OneSource testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Collect plenty of personally identifiable data during a PPDR incident and classify it according to its sensitivity.
Goals	Avoid sensitivity-unaware/mismatched persistent records with PII.
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-3: support the formal definition of various privacy policies (>8).
Risks	R1 – Inadequate management R2 – Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication R3 – Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase R5 – Deviations affecting schedule or budget R6 – A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic R7 – Gaps between needs and developed technology

Table 12 details the roadmap for the Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps asset.

Table 12 - Human-centric Privacy risk management for DevSecOps: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Preliminary version of the asset	M12	T3.1
Preliminary integration with UC4	M18	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Final assessment of the integration with UC4	M24	T5.1

3.3.3. R04: Onboarding Tools

Table 13 presents the integration details between the Onboarding Tools asset and UC4.

Table 13 - Onboarding Tools: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	In the case of a PPDR event, it is necessary to provision a network with the required services for the task. The Onboarding tools will provide a means for the PPDR teams to select the network applications and services that are to be onboarded. These services will offer the desired infrastructure and functions that will aid the operation of these teams.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the human-centric factor of the onboarding tools • Validate the correct onboarding of the network applications and their execution
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI (Framework Deployment): Measure the time taken from the first instruction to deploy the framework until all the services are up and running on the edge/cloud. (<1s)</p> <p>KVI (Zero-touch configuration): Having the configuration/reconfiguration of the end-devices automated, takes a big burden from the support/management teams, while lowering the chances of applying bad configurations and disrupting the operation in course.</p> <p>KVI (Trusted deployment): Due to the sensitivity of the information captured and transmitted, security is a key point. By having guarantees that all network elements that support the deployment are trusted and secured, the overall trustworthiness of the framework is increased.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 – Inadequate management</p> <p>R2 – Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication</p> <p>R3 – Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase</p> <p>R5 – Deviations affecting schedule or budget</p> <p>R6 – A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic</p> <p>R7 – Gaps between needs and developed technology</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components</p> <p>R14 – RIGOROUS applications and services result in slow performance, failing to operate in real-time</p>

Table 14 details the testbed deployment of the Onboarding Tools asset at ONE’s testbed.

Table 14 - Onboarding Tools: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	OneSource testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of this asset • Integration with other assets
Goals	Achieve integration with other assets and validation of this asset for UC4

KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI (Framework Deployment): Measure the time taken from the first instruction to deploy the framework until all the services are up and running on the edge/cloud. (<1s)</p> <p>KVI (Zero-touch configuration): Having the configuration/reconfiguration of the end-devices automated, takes a big burden from the support/management teams, while lowering the chances of applying bad configurations and disrupting the operation in course.</p> <p>KVI (Trusted deployment): Due to the sensitivity of the information captured and transmitted, security is a key point. By having guarantees that all network elements that support the deployment are trusted and secured, the overall trustworthiness of the framework is increased.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 – Inadequate management</p> <p>R2 – Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication</p> <p>R3 – Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase</p> <p>R5 – Deviations affecting schedule or budget</p> <p>R6 – A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic</p> <p>R7 – Gaps between needs and developed technology</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components</p> <p>R14 – RIGOROUS applications and services result in slow performance, failing to operate in real-time</p>

Table 15 details the roadmap for the Onboarding Tools.

Table 15 - Onboarding Tools: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial OpenSlice-based solution with the ability of onboarding network applications	M16	3.1
Orchestration tool above OpenSlice for network application configuration	M18	3.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Design and development of user-friendly human-centric UIs to facilitate the onboarding and design of network applications	M24	3.1

3.3.4. R05: Decentralized services based Identity and Trust management specification

Table 16 details how the specification provided by the Decentralized services based Identity and Trust management specification asset will be used in UC1 and UC3.

Table 16-Decentralized services based Identity and Trust management specification: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1-Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	<p>The 6G system can offer horizontal services (operator’s primary services) and may also offer large number of vertical services (related to third party services) which necessitates more dynamic service specific credentials onboarding for the end-devices i.e., UE (that can be regular UEs or IoTs or devices of anykind) based on the device’s service demands. The service credential in the traditional system is SIM (e.g., USIM/eSIM) based whose activation may take some time and it depends on user document or identification verification (by 3rd parties to perform KYC process). But with the large set of services emerging with 6G, a more dynamic trust management process/mechanism(s) is required, which gives operator more control over the id verification and meanwhile giving the end-users or controllers of the device more control over the user data (i.e., to let the user control their privacy about the level of data that can be exposed with a service provider e.g., a service provider can be a MNO or a 3rd party based on the type of service being requested by the end-device). With the massive number of UEs connecting to the 6G system, a more resilient and secure trust establishment between UE(s) and the 6G network is needed for facilitate quick service credential onboarding and authentication of devices and meanwhile to prevent the network from abusive end-devices/attack vectors (e.g., which launches DoS/DDoS or cyber-attack over the 6G network). Therefore, the asset, ‘Decentralized services-based Identity and Trust management’ can enable the usage of DID (created by the end-device or device controller) to be used during service requests over 6G system to facilitate further service credentials onboarding and authentication. Here, the new PDL services defined as part of the identification and trust management framework can be used by the MNO to query the DID related documents and VCs to validate the DID and to authenticate the end-device/suer associated to the DID by means of cryptographic verifications (e.g., signature verification using the public/secret key available as part of the DID document). The end-device/user can anytime create a DID and link the claims to be disclosed for the services (as needed) and the DID can be stored and managed over any decentralized storage (e.g., a PDL platform) along with the linked DID documents, Verifiable credentials and so on.</p>
Integration objectives	To facilitate usage of user generated DID (includes SSI) for identification and authentication for trust establishment between the end device and the service provider.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	Standards Contributions
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.

	R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.
UC integration	
UC name	UC 3 - Utilities Management and security
Integration description	Physical/IoT devices those need to connect to the Service provider platform through the Gateway, to interface with others meters and sensors and to transmits data & measurements over any available network e.g, such as 6G network may need to get authenticated by the 6G system to use the 6G network as the transport network. Here the asset 'Decentralized services-based Identity and Trust management' can play a significant role to facilitate DID based authentication for the utility devices to use the 6G system. There can be DID controller such as a normal UE (e.g., can belong to a utility manager) which has subscription to the MNO network can generate the DIDs for the utility devices and manage the DIDs along the DID documents and VCs in a storage which is accessible to the MNO (e.g., the storage can also be a decentralized platform like PDL). Whenever the utility devices need to use MNO network, the MNO can authenticate the utility devices based on DIDs to allow it using the MNO network to communicate with the Service provider platform to perform dedicated services.
Integration objectives	To facilitate usage of user generated DID (includes SSI) for identification and authentication for trust establishment between the utility device and the service provider.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	Standards Contributions
Risks	Same as previous

3.3.5. R07: AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments

Table 17 presents the integration details of the AI-Based Security Orchestration across network segments asset with UC1, and UC4.

Table 17 - AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1
Integration description	6G requires impressive network transformation, from dedicated network functions to software network functions, new physical infrastructure deployment, the network virtualisation concepts and new 6G functions. The network transformation from dedicated network functions to software virtualised implementations may open a series of security issues, from physical infrastructure - Physical Network Functions (PNFs), virtualised infrastructure and virtualisation implementation - Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) / Virtual Network Function (VNFs), 6G network functions (Service Based Architecture), 6G Management and Orchestration (MANO), control, and data plane, that may be exposed to several cyber security attacks
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model-based and AI-driven Automated Security Orchestration. • Model-driven Automated Deployment & Security Orchestration at Operations

Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-5: Increased accuracy in orchestration.</p> <p>KPI-6: AI-powered Orchestration of four (04) kinds of resources, namely: services, devices, virtual network functions, and physical network functions.</p> <p>KPI-8: Number of AI Algorithms devised for 6G orchestration >3.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management.</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R11 - Insufficient performance of the ORCHESTRATION mechanisms when applied to multi-domain scenarios.</p>
UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	Use Case 4 focuses on the use of Mobitrust technology, developed by OneSource, in Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) scenarios. It involves the use of different video sources, such as drones or cameras, and the coordination between field teams and Command-and-Control Centre operators. This integration focuses on the Security Orchestrator being able to receive and process MSPL policies from the Decision Engine, designed to apply different actions for Security Agents communicating with cameras, for instance stopping the recording or stopping the streaming of images. With this integration, the Security Orchestrator is able to receive these MSPL policies, process them and generate OpenC2 messages for the cameras, instructing them to perform the action defined in the policy received.
Integration objectives	Model-driven Automated Deployment & Security Orchestration at Operations
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-5: Increased accuracy in orchestration.</p> <p>KPI-6: AI-powered Orchestration of four (04) kinds of resources, namely: services, devices, virtual network functions, and physical network functions.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management.</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R11 - Insufficient performance of the ORCHESTRATION mechanisms when applied to multi-domain scenarios.</p>

Table 18 details the testbed deployment of the AI-Based Security Orchestration across network segments asset at ORO's and ONE's testbeds.

Table 18 - AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO testbed

Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test the capabilities of the orchestrator • Test the first objectives of the orchestrator
Goals	Integrate the SO with different RIGOUROUS functional blocks and with UC1
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-5: Increased accuracy in orchestration.</p> <p>KPI-6: AI-powered Orchestration of four (04) kinds of resources, namely: services, devices, virtual network functions, and physical network functions.</p> <p>KPI-8: Number of AI Algorithms devised for 6G orchestration >3.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management.</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R11 - Insufficient performance of the ORCHESTRATION mechanisms when applied to multi-domain scenarios.</p>
Testbed	
Testbed name	ONE testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test the capabilities of the orchestrator • Test the first objectives of the orchestrator
Goals	Integrate the SO with different RIGOUROUS functional blocks and with UC4
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-5: Increased accuracy in orchestration.</p> <p>KPI-6: AI-powered Orchestration of four (04) kinds of resources, namely: services, devices, virtual network functions, and physical network functions.</p> <p>KPI-8: Number of AI Algorithms devised for 6G orchestration >3.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management.</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R11 - Insufficient performance of the ORCHESTRATION mechanisms when applied to multi-domain scenarios.</p>

Table 19 details the roadmap for the AI-Based Security Orchestration across network segments asset.

Table 19 - AI-based Security Orchestration across network segments: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Limited version of the Security Orchestrator, being able to deploy IPsec tunnels in a single domain.	M16	3.2
Updated version of the Security Orchestrator, being able to translate MSPL policies into specific configuration messages for some components.	M16	3.2

Updated version of the Security Orchestrator, being able to deploy IPsec tunnels in multi-domain scenarios.	M20	3.2
Second prototype	Month	Task
Advanced version of the Security Orchestrator, being able to process and generate configuration messages for most components for the different use cases	M25	3.2

3.3.6. R08: Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification

Table 20 presents the integration details between the Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specifications asset and UC1.

Table 20 - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification: Specifications for UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	6G requires impressive network transformation, from dedicated network functions to software network functions, new physical infrastructure deployment, the network virtualisation concepts and new 6G functions. The network transformation from dedicated network functions to software virtualised implementations may open a series of security issues, from physical infrastructure - Physical Network Functions (PNFs), virtualised infrastructure and virtualisation implementation - Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) / Virtual Network Function (VNFs), 6G network functions (Service Based Architecture), 6G Management and Orchestration (MANO), control, and data plane, that may be exposed to several cyber security attacks. Therefore, this asset helps in collecting abnormal/malicious messages which can help in threat detection and further the TESH enables trust score assignment considering the identified threats/attacks to enable sufficient access control security (may also influence improved decision making in network management and operations) by other assets.
Integration objectives	The trust score from the TESH or the ZTM functional block can be utilised by the other components like the security orchestrator, slice manager and the AID in the raking decision on deployments and management.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-33: Facilitate to identify at least 2 threat vectors (e.g., 2 abnormalities in the network that can help to identify a potential threat/attack).
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic. R11 - Insufficient performance of the ORCHESTRATION mechanisms when applied to multi-domain scenarios.

Table 21 details the testbed deployment of the Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specifications asset at ORO's testbed.

Table 21 - Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	Initiated with Open5GS, further may redo experiments to integrate with ORO Test bed, if access and time permits.
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	TESF functionalities to enable threat identification and trust score assignment are the objectives to experiment.
Goals	Identify possible abnormalities to help in threat detection and to assign trust scores
KPIs/KVIs	SDO contributions KPI-33: At least facilitate to identify 2 threat vectors (e.g., 2 abnormalities in the network that can help to identify a potential threat/attack).
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic. R11 - Insufficient performance of the ORCHESTRATION mechanisms when applied to multi-domain scenarios.

Table 22 details the roadmap for the Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification asset.

Table 22- Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Design of the TESH (Full pipeline)	M16	T3.3
1st UE based attack detection realization- Re-registration Attack	M18	T3.3
Second prototype	Month	Task
2nd UE based attack detection realization	M20	T3.3
1 or 2 network based attack detection realization	M20	T3.3
Fully functional modular testing of TESH by addressing – KPI 33	M30	T3.3

3.3.7. R09: IoT bootstrapping specification

Table 23 details how the specification provided by the IoT bootstrapping specification asset will be used in UC2, UC3 and UC4.

Table 23 - IoT bootstrapping specification: Specifications for UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC2 - Digital City Twining Platform

Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the asset specification defined in the deliverable D3.1, clause 5.2.1.1 and can be applied to any device/UE in the use case. The specification describes the procedures on how devices first connect to the onboarding network, gets authenticated, and authorized for long-term credential provisioning. The long-term credentials are then used for authenticated network access.
Integration objectives	Ensure that only trusted and authenticated devices are considered for network access.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>Framework Deployment: Measure the time taken from the first instruction to deploy the framework until all the services are up and running on the edge/cloud (<1s).</p> <p>End-to-end slicing: Measure the time taken for the configuration of the new slice across the different network segments (<1s).</p> <p>BYOD trust analysis: Measure the time taken to analyse the device and deem it secure/insecure to be used in the operation (<1s).</p> <p>Device bootstrapping: Measure the time taken for the bootstrapping of the enddevices with all needed configurations (<1s).</p> <p>KPI-11: OPEX reduction in detection, decision, and mitigation (-15%).</p> <p>KPI-5: Increased accuracy in orchestration (+10%).</p> <p>This KPIs/KVIs are defined in 6.2.1.3 of deliverable D2.2 with respect to Device bootstrapping, BYOD trust analysis, Zero-touch configuration.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management.</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p>
UC integration	
UC name	UC3 - Utilities Management and Security
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the asset specification defined in the deliverable D3.1, clause 5.2.1.1 and can be applied to any device/UE in the use case. The specification describes the procedures on how devices first connect to the onboarding network, gets authenticated, and authorized for long-term credential provisioning. The long-term credentials are then used for authenticated network access.
Integration objectives	Ensure that only trusted and authenticated devices are considered for network access.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	Same as previous.
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management.</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p>
UC integration	
UC name	UC4 - PPDR IoT Situational Awareness Platform

Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the asset specification defined in the deliverable D3.1, clause 5.2.1.1 and can be applied to any device/UE in the use case. The specification describes the procedures on how devices first connect to the onboarding network, gets authenticated, and authorized for long-term credential provisioning. The long-term credentials are then used for authenticated network access.
Integration objectives	Ensure that only trusted and authenticated devices are considered for network access.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	Same as previous.
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.

3.3.8. R10: Trusted application onboarding specification

Table 24 details how the specification provided by the Trusted application onboarding specification asset will be used in UC3 and UC4.

Table 24 - Trusted application onboarding specification: Specifications for UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC3 - Utilities Management and Security
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the asset specification defined in the deliverable D3.1, clause 5.2.1.2 and can be applied to any required application in the use case. The specification describes the procedures on how to provide information from the trusted network function to the UE in order to ensure that trusted applications are installed on the UE, that may use privileged resources.
Integration objectives	Ensure that only trusted applications are considered for network access.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	Same as stated in Table 23.
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.
UC integration	
UC name	UC4 - PPDR IoT Situational Awareness Platform
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the asset specification defined in the deliverable D3.1, clause 5.2.1.2 and can be applied to any required application

	in the use case. The specification describes the procedures on how to provide information from the trusted network function to the UE in order to ensure that trusted applications are installed on the UE, that may use privileged resources.
Integration objectives	Ensure that only trusted applications are considered for network access.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	Same as stated in Table 23.
Risks	R1 - Inadequate management. R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase. R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget. R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.

3.3.9. R11: Slice Manager

Table 25 presents the integration details between the Slice Manager asset and UC1.

Table 25 - Slice Manager: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	The Slice Manager is a centralized component that will provide E2E network slicing capabilities across different segments of the 5G/6G infrastructure. This component offers a NBI interface to Security Orchestrator (OS) to allow the enforcement of Security Policies in the infrastructure as E2E slices.
Integration objectives	Multi-domain automated end-to-end slicing as a mechanism to protect the infrastructure and services from cyber-attacks.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-9: Number of concurrent end-to-end slices supported ≥ 2048 KPI-10: Number of concurrent devices supported in the cognitive network management. KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA. KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOROUS: <1 minute).
Risks	RM1: Inadequate management. RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase. RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations. RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget. RT2: Lack of integration among tools. RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation

	<p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/ trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>
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Table 26 details the testbed deployment of the Slice Manager asset at ORO's testbed.

Table 26 - Slice Manager: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To validate the enforcement of an E2E slices in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. To validate the RIGOUROUS KPIs associated to this component in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. Integration with the RIGOUROUS components involved in the UC1.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To deploy in OROs testbed the Slice Manager. Validate the component functionality. Performance evaluation in a real 5G/6G testbed. Integration with RIGOUROUS framework components involved in use case I.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-9: Number of concurrent end-to-end slices supported ≥ 2048</p> <p>KPI-10: Number of concurrent devices supported in the cognitive network management.</p> <p>KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA.</p> <p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1 minute).</p>
Risks	<p>RM1: Inadequate management.</p> <p>RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation</p> <p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/ trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>

Table 27 details the roadmap for the Slice Manager asset.

Table 27 - Slice Manager: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
RIGOROUS requirement analysis for the component	M5	T3.4
Literature review	M5	T3.4
Architectural design (sub-components and functionalities)	M7	T3.4
E2E Slice Engine implementation	M12	T3.4
Security Control Agent (SBI with NSP) implementation	M14	T3.4
WEB GUI implementation	M16	T3.4
REST API NBI implementation	M16	T3.4
Standalone validation and performance evaluation in UWS testbed	M18	T3.4
Deployment and Integration in OROs testbed	M18	T3.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
First integration design iteration	M18	T3.4
Integration process in OROs testbed (refining and polishing)	M23	T3.4
Final version of the component deployed in OROs testbed	M26	T3.4
KPIs: Empirical tests and results for functional validation	M28	T3.4
KPIs: Empirical tests and results for performance evaluation	M30	T3.4

3.3.10.R11: Network Self-Protection

Table 28 presents the integration details between the Network Self-Protection asset and UC1.

Table 28 - Network Self-Protection: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	<p>One of main challenges when dealing with multi-tenant multi-domain 6G infrastructures is to deal with network traffic inherent to this kind of networks. That is, nested traffic with different levels of encapsulation in order to provide user mobility and tenants isolation. Regarding the protection of the infrastructure at data plane level, The Network Sel-Protection provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A fine-grained traffic classifier able to handle with the type of overlay traffic and protocol expected in 6G such as VLAN, GTP, VXLAN or, GRE. • Network Slicing mechanism able to apply security policies in the data plane as network slices to mitigate the impact of cyber incidents. • North Bound (NB) interface with extended data plane programmability beyond the current SotA.
Integration objectives	Enable Network Slicing capabilities in the data plane as a mechanism to stop malicious traffic, mitigating the impact of cyber incidents where the infrastructure or services are targeted.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-9: Number of concurrent end-to-end slices supported ≥ 2048

	KPI-10: Number of concurrent devices supported in the cognitive network management.
Risks	<p>RM1: Inadequate management.</p> <p>RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation</p> <p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/ trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>

Table 29 details the testbed deployment of the Network Self-Protection asset at ORO's testbed.

Table 29 - Network Self-Protection: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To validate the enforcement of the network slices in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. To evaluate the performance and validate its KPIs in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. To integrate with other RIGUROUS architectural components involved in the use case.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To deploy in OROs testbed the Network Self-Protection component. Validate the component functionality Performance evaluation in a real 5G/6G test-bed Integration with RIGUROUS framework components involved in use case I.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-9: Number of concurrent end-to-end slices supported ≥ 2048</p> <p>KPI-10: Number of concurrent devices supported in the cognitive network management.</p>
Risks	<p>RM1: Inadequate management.</p> <p>RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation.</p>

	<p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>
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Table 30 details the roadmap for the Network Self-Protection asset.

Table 30 - Network Self-Protection: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
RIGOROUS requirement analysis for the component	M5	T3.4
Literature review	M5	T3.4
Architectural design (sub-components and functionalities)	M7	T3.4
6G Multi-tenant Traffic Classifier implementation	M12	T3.4
Open Flow protocol extension to deal with 5G/6S traffic	M13	T3.4
Internal APIs and network slicing capabilities	M14	T3.4
North Bound Interface with Slice Manager	M15	T3.4
Standalone validation and performance evaluation in UWS testbed	M16	T3.4
Deployment and Integration in OROs testbed	M18	T3.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
First integration design iteration	M18	T3.4
Integration process in OROs testbed (refining and polishing)	M23	T3.4
Final version of the component deployed in OROs testbed	M26	T3.4
KPIs: Empirical tests and results for functional validation	M28	T3.4
KPIs: Empirical tests and results for performance evaluation	M30	T3.4

3.3.11.R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework

Table 31 presents the integration details between the Holistic Security and Privacy Framework asset and UC4.

Table 31 - Holistic Security and Privacy Framework: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	The HSPF will be integrated with UC4 to provide network traffic anomaly detection over the inbound and outbound communications of the Mobitrust application. The HSPF components will be injected as sidecars next to the UC4 micro-services, where they will collect and classify the network traffic. Additionally, the HSPF components will perform continuous federated training rounds, in order to update the ML models, thus keeping them up to date with the ever-changing network traffic characteristics.

Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate the correct functioning of the HSPF into detecting network traffic anomalies • Assess the HSPF performance on detecting different attacks • Validate the integration between the HSPF and the RIGOUROUS Security Analytics Engine (SAE) component, using a RIGOUROUS UC
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-12: The continuous development of the HSPF and respective validation next to the UC4 micro-services will contribute to the reduction of false alarms by (at least) 30%.</p> <p>KPI-13: The continuous development of the HSPF and respective validation next to the UC4 micro-services will contribute to the increase of accuracy in the identification of network anomalies (> 95%).</p> <p>KPI-21: The increase of accuracy in the identification of network anomalies, linked with the decrease of false alarms will result in the output of accurate information for the RIGOUROUS components, which will ultimately contribute to the improvement of decision-making process.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays in the integration with the UC • Delays in the integration with the RIGOUROUS SAE component

Table 32 details the testbed deployment of the Holistic Security and Privacy Framework asset at ONE and UMU testbeds.

Table 32 - Holistic Security and Privacy Framework: Testbeds deployment

Testbed	
Testbed name	ONE
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Development, testing and validation of the Asset Integration with UC4
Goals	Integrate this Asset with other Assets and UCs
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-24: The deployment of the HSPF at ONE will enable its validation from an early stage, contributing to its readiness state for integrations with UCs and other Assets. This deployment will also be used for potential preliminary integrations with other components, before proceeding to its integration into the RIGOUROUS framework.</p> <p>KPI-30: The deployment of the HSPF at ONE, will enable its integration with the UC4 and later demonstration.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties with the remote access to the testbed • Required HW settings not available (AVX-512 instruction set, at least)
Testbed	
Testbed name	UMU
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Integration with the RIGOUROUS framework (namely, the SAE component)
Goals	Integrate the HSPF Asset with the RIGOUROUS framework

KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-24: The deployment of the HSPF at UMU will be conducted following an Agile procedure. There will be periodic meetings between all the involved partners in order to check on the integration status between the HSPF and the remaining RIGOUROUS components. Moreover, additional measures will be taken every time a specific problem is delaying the integration process, like direct dialogue (i.e., using chat tools) or additional (virtual) meetings.</p> <p>KPI-30: The deployment of the HSPF at UMU, will enable its integration with the RIGOUROUS framework and later demonstration.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties with the remote access to the testbed • Required HW settings not available (AVX-512 instruction set, at least) • Difficulties throughout the integration process with the RIGOUROUS framework

Table 33 details the roadmap for the Holistic Security and Privacy Framework asset.

Table 33 - Holistic Security and Privacy Framework: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial deployment at ONE	M13	T4.1
Preliminary integration with UC4 at ONE	M14	T5.1
Initial deployment at UMU	M14	T5.1
Preliminary integration with RIGOUROUS framework at UMU	M15	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Integration with UC4: assessment and validation	M20	T5.1
Stable integration with the RIGOUROUS framework	M22	T5.1
Completed integration with UC4 and with the RIGOUROUS framework	M24	T5.1

3.3.12.R12: Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector

Table 34 presents the integration details between the Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset and UC2.

Table 34: Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC2
Integration description	<p>In UC2, Threat Scenario 1, the Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset (OULU) will be integrated with the Encryption as a Service (EaaS) asset (ICTFI) to leverage the Homomorphic Encryption (HE) service provided by EaaS platform for encrypting and decrypting the parameters of local models shared with the aggregation server.</p> <p>The infrastructure will be equipped with several FL clients as well as a FL Aggregator, which will be used to train a detection model (MLP/CNN model) using data features to differentiate between attacks and normal samples. In</p>

	<p>addition, FL clients will encrypt their local model parameters so that sharing parameters with the FL Aggregator will be secure. To this end, the EaaS's HE service will be used.</p> <p>To validate the final model, after Federated Learning has been performed using existing data, the final model can be used for attack detection/classification.</p>
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detecting anomalies based on existing data and previously trained FL-based deep learning models. • Integrating HE to enhance privacy and data confidentiality through the facilitation of secure data sharing. • Validate that the model correctly classes anomalous data according to the type of attack and that it has achieved the target accuracy throughout the training process.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-12: Reduction of false alarms at least 30%</p> <p>KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%</p> <p>KPI-16: The number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10.</p> <p>Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector will contribute to this project's KPI by detecting some kinds of attacks related to Command injection, Response injection, DDoS, and reconnaissance.</p>
Risks	Delays in the integration with the UC and EaaS component.

Table 35 details the testbed deployment of the Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset at the ICTFI testbed.

Table 35 - Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ICTFI
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Integration and validation of the asset's components with UC2
Goals	Integrate this asset with ICTFI's EaaS asset
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-30: The deployment of the Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset at ICTFI will enable its integration with EaaS asset as part of UC2 and later demonstration.
Risks	Difficulties with remote access to the testbed

Table 36 details the roadmap for the Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset.

Table 36 - Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
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Simulated FL training and anomaly detection (binary classification) using publicly available datasets.	M16	T4.1
Development of the asset's APIs	M17	T5.1
Initial integration with ICTFI's EaaS asset	M18	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Stable version of the asset's API	M20	T5.1
Assessment of the integration with the ICTFI's EaaS asset	M24	T5.1

3.3.13.R12: Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection

Table 37 presents the integration details between the Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection asset and UC4.

Table 37 - Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	In UC4-Scenario 2, the Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection asset (UMU) will be integrated for real-time monitoring, anomaly detection and attack classification so that mitigation agents, such as the AI-driven Decision Engine, can receive the alerts with the necessary information to come up with the optimal set of countermeasures to mitigate the attacks taking place at a certain moment. Several FL Agents, as well as FL Aggregators, will be deployed in the infrastructure as Security Agents by the Security Orchestrator, so they can collect traffic flow features and train a detection model (Deep Autoencoder) that will be able to discern between non-anomalous and anomalous/attack flow samples, which will be later classified as known attack types or, if not possible, as a potential zero-day/unknown attack. For validation, a set of attack scripts (both for user-plane and control-plane attacks) can be executed, data can be collected and, after Federated Learning is performed, the final model can be used for real-time attack detection and alerting.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor and inject real-time benign/normal traffic flow features to the FL agents for training the anomaly detection model. • Monitor and inject real-time benign/malicious traffic flow features to the detection engine for anomaly detection (using the previously trained model and some scripts for simulating the attack scenarios and generate the malicious data). • Verify that the model achieves the target accuracy on training phase, and that anomalous flows are classified into specific attack types and alerted properly to the AI-based Decision Engine
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-13: increase of accuracy in anomaly detection (>95%)</p> <p>KPI-14: time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)</p>

	<p>KVI (Secured Platform): The security measures taken from the beginning increase the overall base security, reducing the chances for possible attacks or manipulations of the framework. This then guarantees smoother management of the operations, increasing the potential success of the actions being taken.</p> <p>KVI (Decreased interferences and downtime): Despite the increased based security, some attacks or interferences might still occur. Decreasing the time taken to detect and mitigate those cases can lead to less impact on the ongoing actions, preventing possible riskier scenarios due to system unavailability.</p>
Risks	<p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology.</p> <p>R12 - Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes.</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>R19 - Results if the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated</p>

Table 38 details the testbed deployment of the Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection asset at UMU and ONE testbeds.

Table 38 - Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	UMU Testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry out the first tests to extract preliminary results prior to real deployment in UC4/OneSource testbed.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deploy, configure, and integrate successfully the components related to the asset: FL Agent, FL Aggregator, Anomaly Detection Engine, Attack Classification Engine and Kafka broker for data ingestion/anomaly alerts publication. Generate and ingest the needed data for training and evaluation, regarding different types of attacks (CP/UP) and benign traffic. For this purpose, existing monitoring and flow-processing tools in UMU testbed will be integrated and used, and also scripts to simulate both the benign traffic and the attack-related traffic.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-13: increase of accuracy in anomaly detection (>95%)</p> <p>KPI-14: time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)</p>

	<p>KVI (Secured Platform): The security measures taken from the beginning increase the overall base security, reducing the chances for possible attacks or manipulations of the framework. This then guarantees smoother management of the operations, increasing the potential success of the actions being taken.</p> <p>KVI (Decreased interferences and downtime): Despite the increased based security, some attacks or interferences might still occur. Decreasing the time taken to detect and mitigate those cases can lead to less impact on the ongoing actions, preventing possible riskier scenarios due to system unavailability.</p>
Risks	<p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology.</p> <p>R12 - Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes.</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p>
Testbed	
Testbed name	OneSource Testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration with the Scenario 3 of UC4 (Intrusion into system to access privileged information or cause disruption of services) Achieve objective R12: Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector. Continuous monitoring for potential attacks and anomalies increases the response time for mitigation actions and recovery actions.
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deploy, configure, and integrate successfully the components related to the asset: FL Agent, FL Aggregator, Anomaly Detection Engine, Attack Classification Engine and Kafka broker for data ingestion/anomaly alerts publication. Generate and ingest the needed data for training and evaluation, regarding different types of attacks (CP/UP) and benign traffic.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-13: increase of accuracy in anomaly detection (>95%)</p> <p>KPI-14: time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)</p> <p>KVI (Secured Platform): The security measures taken from the beginning increase the overall base security, reducing the chances for possible attacks or manipulations of the framework. This then guarantees smoother management of the operations, increasing the potential success of the actions being taken.</p> <p>KVI (Decreased interferences and downtime): Despite the increased based security, some attacks or interferences might still occur. Decreasing the time taken to detect and mitigate those cases can lead to less impact on the</p>

	ongoing actions, preventing possible riskier scenarios due to system unavailability.
Risks	<p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology.</p> <p>R12 - Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes.</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>R19 - Results if the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>

Table 39 details the roadmap for the Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection asset.

Table 39 - Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Simulated FL training and anomaly detection (binary classification) using publicly available datasets.	M16	T4.1
Attack classification (multi-class classification) using publicly available datasets	M16	T4.1
Integration of Differential Privacy techniques within the FL process and first results	M17	T4.1
Implementation of the interfaces according to the agreed specific data models	M17	T4.1
First version of orchestrable FL agents/aggregators integrating DP available to be deployed in the corresponding testbeds	M18	T4.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Modifications of the interfaces data models according to the last updates	M20	T4.1
Implementation and evaluation of new Differential Privacy techniques integrated within the FL process and extract more advanced results	M24	T4.1
Second version of orchestrable FL agents/aggregators integrating DP available to be deployed in the corresponding testbeds	M26	T4.1
Anomaly detection and attack classification using real traffic information from the testbeds	M28	T4.1
Results of real anomaly detection/attack classification to be included in D4.3	M30	T4.1

3.3.14.R13: AI-powered EDoS Mitigator

Table 40 presents the integration details between the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset and UC2.

Table 40 - AI-powered EDoS Mitigato: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC2
Integration description	The asset will be demonstrated in Scenario 3 of UC2. The EDoS Mitigator will be integrated with the Auto-scaling module of the cloud-native platform, such as Horizontal Pod Autoscaling (HPA) of Kubernetes, to assess the legitimacy or maliciousness of resource scaling of a given service deployed on the cloud-native platform. When an auto-scaling request is issued to create new replicas, the request is intercepted by the “Admission Controller” and then delegated to the EDoS Mitigator for validation. When the delegation request is received, the EDoS Mitigator will compare the values of the observed resource usage and performance metrics with the ones forecasted by the Deep Learning model incorporated in EDoS Mitigator. If the observed values deviate considerably from the predicted ones, the scaling request is flagged as malicious and will be refused by the Admission Controller.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate the correct functioning of the EDoS Mitigator into proactively mitigating EDoS attacks by preventing malicious scaling requests caused by application-layer DDoS attacks. • Assess performance of EDoS Mitigator in detecting application-layer DDoS attacks and reducing the economic damage. • Validate the integration between the EDoS Mitigator and the RIGOUROUS Response-Mitigation component, using a RIGOUROUS UC.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-12: Reduction of false alarms at least 30%</p> <p>KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%</p> <p>KPI-16: Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10. EDoS Mitigator will contribute to this project’s KPI by detecting two kinds of DDoS attacks (Slowloris and Hulk)</p> <p>KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5%</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays in the integration with the UC • Delays in the integration with the RIGOUROUS Response-Mitigation component

Table 41 details the testbed deployment of the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator Detection asset at OULU and ICTFI testbeds.

Table 41 - AI-powered EDoS Mitigator: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	OULU

Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development, testing and validation of the asset integration with UC2. Generate and ingest the data needed for training and evaluation, considering HTTP-based application-layer DDoS attacks.
Goals	Demonstrate how EDoS Mitigator asset can prevent malicious K8s' HPA requests triggered by malicious UEs launching an application-layer DDoS attack against the vCDN slice.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-12: Reduction of false alarms at least 30%</p> <p>KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%</p> <p>KPI-16: Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10. EDoS Mitigator will contribute to this project's KPI by detecting two kinds of DDoS attacks (Slowloris and Hulk)</p> <p>KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5%</p>
Risks	DL model with low performance during serving phase compared to its training performances
Testbed	
Testbed name	ICTFI
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Deployment, integration, and validation of the asset's components (EDoS Mitigator, Admission Controller, and Monitoring System) with UC2
Goals	Demonstrate how EDoS Mitigator asset can prevent malicious K8s' HPA requests generated by malicious IoT devices launching an application-layer DDoS attack against the Video-on-Demand (VoD) service of ICTFI's DTB.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-12: Reduction of false alarms at least 30%</p> <p>KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%</p> <p>KPI-16: Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10. EDoS Mitigator will contribute to this project's KPI by detecting two kinds of DDoS attacks (Slowloris and Hulk)</p> <p>KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5%</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulties with remote access to the testbed Need to retrain the DL model to adapt to the new environment

Table 42 details the roadmap for the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator Detection asset.

Table 42 - AI-powered EDoS Mitigator: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial deployment at OULU	M16	T4.1
Initial deployment at ICTFI	M17	T5.1
Preliminary integration with UC2 at ICTFI	M18	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Integration with UC2: assessment and validation	M20	T5.1

3.3.15.R14: MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)

Table 43 presents the integration details between the MTD-based Robust ML Model(s) asset and UC4.

Table 43 - MTD-based Robust ML Model(s): UCs Integration.

UC integration	
UC name	Use Case IV
Integration description	It will be integrated with the thread scenario “Intrusion into system to access privileged information or cause disruption of services”. FL can be applied for attack detection to increase the security of the service operation. Model poisoning is an intrusion that can reduce the attack detection accuracy. A multi-model-based FL will be applied as an MTD approach to deal with model poisoning attack.
Integration objectives	Integrating a multi-model-based FL as MTD approach to increase the attack detection accuracy.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection KPI-18: Increase the resilience of ML models to adversarial attacks
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaining low accuracy on the specific data in the context of UC4 • Low speed of data transmission during training, as data is gained by calling services of Data Provider

Table 44 details the testbed deployment of the MTD-based Robust ML Model(s) asset at the OULU testbeds.

Table 44 - MTD-based Robust ML Model(s): Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	OULU
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Integration and validation of asset’s component with UC4
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make FLaaS provided by ONE robust by MTD • Illustrate the robustness of FL boosted by MTD for specific data in the context of UC4
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection KPI-18: Increase the resilience of ML models to adversarial attacks
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaining low accuracy on the specific data in the context of UC4 • Low speed of data transmission during training, as data is gained by calling services of Data Provider

Table 45 details the roadmap for the MTD-based Robust ML Model(s) asset.

Table 45 - MTD-based Robust ML Model(s): Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
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First implementation of the asset integration with UC4	M18	T4.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Intermediate implementation of the asset integration with UC4	M24	T5.1
First Implementation-In-Lab-testing	M20	T5.2
Intermediate Implementation-In-Lab-testing	M26	T5.2
Final Integration of asset with UC IV	M32	T5.2
Final Implementation-In-Lab-testing	M34	T5.2

3.3.16.R15: Dynamic and Automated Service Composition

Table 46 presents the integration details between the Dynamic and Automated Service Composition asset and UC3.

Table 46 - Dynamic and Automated Service Composition: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	Use Case #3 – Utilities Management and security
Integration description	In Use Case 3, DASC will detect mismatches and interconnection problems among different components that are attempting to interoperate. When a mismatch is detected, Dynamic automated service composition suggests some conversions to overcome the issue.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect interconnection problems among different components • Categorizes the causes that cause the mismatches
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection</p> <p>KPI-14: Time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)</p> <p>KPI-18: Increase the resilience of ML models to adversarial attacks</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes • Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components

Table 47 details the testbed deployment of the Dynamic and Automated Service Composition asset at the WINGS testbed.

Table 47 - Dynamic and Automated Service Composition: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	WINGS testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate DASC • Integrate DASC in RIGOUROUS architecture
Goals	Successful function of DASC and integration with other assets
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection</p> <p>KPI-14: Time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)</p>

	KPI-18: Increase the resilience of ML models to adversarial attacks
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components

Table 48 details the roadmap for the Dynamic and Automated Service Composition asset.

Table 48 - Dynamic and Automated Service Composition: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
First version of DASC using open datasets	M16	T4.2
Deployment at WINGS testbed	M22	T5.1
Integration with UC3	M24	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Final integration with UC3	M32	T5.2
Final asset version	M34	T5.2

3.3.17.R15: Digital Twin

Table 49 presents the integration details between the Digital Twin asset and UC3.

Table 49 - Digital Twin: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	Use Case #3 - Utilities Management and security
Integration description	In Use Case 3, Digital Twin provides a simulation of a system that consists of different components that communicate with each other. This input is sent to the Dynamic automated service composition so that it can identify the mismatches in the communication between the different components and propose solutions.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides simulation regarding the capability of different components to interoperate. Provides input to Dynamic automated service composition in order to identify the causes of the mismatches and propose solutions.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-5: Protection of 6G Services against Cyber Threats
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components

Table 50 details the testbed deployment of the Digital Twin asset at WINGS's testbed.

Table 50 - Digital Twin: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
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Testbed name	WINGS testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Validate Digital Twin and the communication with DASC
Goals	Successful function of Digital Twin and integration with other assets
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-5: Protection of 6G Services against Cyber Threats
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components

Table 51 details the roadmap for the Digital Twin asset.

Table 51 - Digital Twin: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
First version of Digital Twin	M16	T4.2
Deployment at WINGS testbed	M22	T5.1
Integration with UC3	M24	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Final integration with UC3	M32	T5.2
Final asset version	M34	T5.2

3.3.18.R16: AI-driven decision making

Table 52 presents the integration details of the AI-driven decision making asset with UC1, UC2, UC3 and UC4.

Table 52 - AI-driven decision making: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1 - Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC1 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC1 which will be implemented on the ORO testbed.</p> <p>KPI-11: OPEX reduction by at least 15% in detection, decision, and mitigation. KPI-12: Reduction of false alarms by at least 30%. KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%. KPI-14: Time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds KPI-16: Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10.</p>

	<p>KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5%</p> <p>KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA</p> <p>KPI-21: Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to SOTA</p> <p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS:<1min)</p> <p>KPI-23: Early-stage Security Threat Warning time optimization by 70%.</p> <p>KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases using conditions based real operational environments.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interfaces not prepared on time • Lack of integration fabric/platform • Lack of appropriate input data for the UC
UC integration	
UC name	UC2 - Digital City Twining Platform
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC2 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC2 which will be implemented on the ICTFI testbed.</p> <p>The detailed list of KPIs is equal to the one specified for UC1.</p>
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for UC1.
UC integration	
UC name	UC3 - Utilities Management and Security
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC3 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC3 which will be implemented on the WINGS testbed.</p> <p>The detailed list of KPIs is equal to the one specified for UC1.</p>
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for UC1.
UC integration	
UC name	UC4 - PPDR IoT Situational Awareness Platform

Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC4 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC4 which will be implemented on the ONE testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is equal to the one specified for UC1.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for UC1.

Table 53 details the testbed deployment of the AI-driven decision making asset at ORO, ICTFI, WINGS, ONE and EBOS testbeds.

Table 53 - AI-driven decision making: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AID will be deployed on ORO testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC1 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC1 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC1 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC1 which will be implemented on the ORO testbed. KPI-11: OPEX reduction by at least 15% in detection, decision, and mitigation. KPI-12: Reduction of false alarms by at least 30%. KPI-13: Increase of accuracy in anomaly detection to exceed > 95%. KPI-14: Time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds KPI-16: Number of kinds of Cyberattacks detected through AI > 10. KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5% KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA KPI-21: Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to SOTA KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS:<1min) KPI-23: Early-stage Security Threat Warning time optimization by 70%.

	KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases using conditions based real operational environments.
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other necessary assets not deployed on time on the testbed • Testbed not supporting appropriate integration fabric on time
Testbed	
Testbed name	ICTFI
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AID will be deployed on ICTFI testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC2 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC2 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC2 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC2 which will be implemented on the ICTFI testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.
Testbed	
Testbed name	WINGS
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AID will be deployed on WINGS testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC3 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC3 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC3 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC3 which will be implemented on the WINGS testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.
Testbed	
Testbed name	ONE
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AID will be deployed on ONE testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC4 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC4 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC4 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.

KPIs/KVIs	The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC4 which will be implemented on the ONE testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.
Testbed	
Testbed name	EBOS
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AID will be deployed on EBOS testbed for InLab testing purposes to verify integration and functionality.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, testing accordingly and achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AID asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs. Thus, testing its functionality and integration with adjacent assets in the RIGOUROUS architecture on the EBOS testbed contributes towards achieving these KPIs. The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.

Table 54 details the roadmap for the AI-driven decision making asset.

Table 54 - AI-driven decision making: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Taxonomy preparation with open data sets and communication with TRA	M15	T4.3
Creation of the risk assessment matrix with open data sets	M16	T4.3
Combination of the risk assessment matrix and values received from TRA	M17	T4.3
Preparation of deep neural network algorithm for mitigation actions	M19	T4.3
Integration with architecture	M20	T4.3
Second prototype	Month	Task
Communication with RM	M18	T4.3
Receive inputs from all partners	M20	T4.3
Harmonise partners input with the internal taxonomy system	M22	T4.3
Communication with the Security Orchestrator	M24	T4.3
Final deployment	M28	T4.3

3.3.19.R16: AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision

Table 55 presents the integration details of the AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision asset with UC1, UC2, UC3 and UC4.

Table 55 - AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1 - Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC1 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC1 which will be implemented on the ORO testbed.</p> <p>KPI-11: OPEX reduction by at least 15% in detection, decision, and mitigation.</p> <p>KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5%</p> <p>KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA</p> <p>KPI-21: Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to SOTA</p> <p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS:<1min)</p> <p>KPI-23: Early-stage Security Threat Warning time optimization by 70%.</p> <p>KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases using conditions based real operational environments.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interfaces not prepared on time • Lack of integration fabric/platform • Lack of appropriate input data for the UC
UC integration	
UC name	UC2 - Digital City Twining Platform
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC2 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC2 which will be implemented on the ICTFI testbed.</p> <p>The detailed list of KPIs is equal to the one specified for UC1.</p>
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for UC1.
UC integration	

UC name	UC3 - Utilities Management and Security
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC3 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC3 which will be implemented on the WINGS testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is equal to the one specified for UC1.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for UC1.
UC integration	
UC name	UC4 - PPDR IoT Situational Awareness Platform
Integration description	The asset will be integrated through the interfaces defined in the Interfaces List section below, with the proper assets also participating in UC4 as per the RIGOUROUS architecture.
Integration objectives	Transfer of appropriate data as inputs and outputs of the asset
Specific KPIs/KVIs	The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC4 which will be implemented on the ONE testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is equal to the one specified for UC1.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for UC1.

Table 56 details the testbed deployment of the AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision asset at the ORO, ICTFI, WINGS, ONE and the EBOS testbed.

Table 56 - AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AI-RM will be deployed on ORO testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC1 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC1 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions and communicate them through MSPL to SO.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC1 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC1 which will be implemented on the ORO testbed. KPI-11: OPEX reduction by at least 15% in detection, decision, and mitigation.

	<p>KPI-19: Reduce the allowed malicious scale-up operations due to EDoS attacks to be < 5%</p> <p>KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA</p> <p>KPI-21: Improve decision-making on threat mitigation by 45% compared to SOTA</p> <p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS:<1min)</p> <p>KPI-23: Early-stage Security Threat Warning time optimization by 70%.</p> <p>KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases using conditions based real operational environments.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other necessary assets not deployed on time on the testbed • Testbed not supporting appropriate integration fabric on time
Testbed	
Testbed name	ICTFI
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AI-RM will be deployed on ICTFI testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC2 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC2 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions and communicate them through MSPL to SO.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC2 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC2 which will be implemented on the ICTFI testbed.</p> <p>The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.</p>
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.
Testbed	
Testbed name	WINGS
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AI-RM will be deployed on WINGS testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC3 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC3 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions and communicate them through MSPL to SO.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC3 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC3 which will be implemented on the WINGS testbed.</p> <p>The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.</p>
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.
Testbed	

Testbed name	ONE
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AI-RM will be deployed on ONE testbed to satisfy the objectives of UC4 which will be demonstrated on this testbed. AID will take decisions on attacks taking place in UC4 and communicate relevant information to AI-RM to determine mitigation actions and communicate them through MSPL to SO.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, in the UC4 scenarios set-up, to be implemented on this testbed, achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs which will be evaluated in the different use case scenarios including UC4 which will be implemented on the ONE testbed. The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.
Testbed	
Testbed name	EBOS
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	AI-RM will be deployed on EBOS testbed for Inlab testing purposes to verify integration and functionality.
Goals	Enable end to end RIGOUROUS functionality in terms of threat detection, decision, mitigation flow, testing accordingly and achieving the appropriate KPIs as mentioned below.
KPIs/KVIs	The AI-RM asset based on its functionality and its central role in the whole detection-decision-mitigation flow is involved in the following KPIs. Thus, testing its functionality and integration with adjacent assets in the RIGOUROUS architecture on the EBOS testbed contributes towards achieving these KPIs. The detailed list of KPIs is similar to the one specified for ORO deployment.
Risks	Equal to the ones specified for ORO deployment.

Table 57 details the roadmap for the AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision asset.

Table 57 - AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Build an algorithm for mitigation actions taking into account Efficiency vs QoS vs Security	M18	T4.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
Receive inputs from AID	M18	T4.4
Receive inputs from all partners	M20	T4.4
Final algorithm output	M26	T4.4
Communication with all partners	M28	T4.4
Final deployment	M30	T4.4

3.3.20.R18: Cyber Physical Correlator

Table 58 presents the integration details between the Cyber Physical Correlator asset and UC3.

Table 58 - Cyber Physical Correlator: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	Use Case #3 – Utilities Management and security
Integration description	In Use Case 3, Cyber-Physical Correlator will monitor the network traffic in order to detect attacks. The tool will also classify the attacks in categories (false data injection, DDoS, man in the middle) and communicate with AI-driven to provide all the information about the attack. In this way Cyber-Physical Correlator will contribute to the security of the communication of smart meters with the cloud.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor network traffic flow to detect possible attacks • Classify the detected attack into different classes • Provide information to AID about the attacks • Validate the accuracy of the model
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI-13: increase of accuracy in anomaly detection (>95%) • KPI-14: time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication • Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes • Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components

Table 59 details the testbed deployment of the Cyber Physical Correlator asset at the WINGS testbed.

Table 59 - Cyber Physical Correlator: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	WINGS testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Validate Cyber-Physical Correlator Integrate Cyber-Physical Correlator in RIGOUROUS architecture
Goals	Successful function of Cyber-Physical Correlator and integration with other assets
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-13: increase of accuracy in anomaly detection (>95%) KPI-14: time to detection to reach real-time detection of order of milliseconds (<1s)
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication • Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components
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Table 60 details the roadmap for the Cyber Physical Correlator asset.

Table 60 - Cyber Physical Correlator: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
First version of Cyber-Physical Correlator using open datasets	M16	T4.3
Deployment at WINGS testbed	M22	T5.1
Integration with UC3	M24	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Final integration with UC3	M32	T5.2
Final asset version	M34	T5.2

3.3.21.R19: Threat Risk Assessor

Table 61 presents the integration details of the Threat Risk Assessor asset with UC1, UC3 and UC4.

Table 61 Threat Risk assessor: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1 - Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats.
Integration description	The use case to be piloted will validate the capacity and capabilities of the platform to increase the resilience of the Telecommunication infrastructures by protecting against threats to services offered by Orange Romania.
Integration objectives	Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Dynamic Risk Assessment and Mitigation Strategies leveraging Anomaly Detection capabilities across ORO Network Layers within a continuous risk assessment loop enable an increase in response and mitigation capabilities against cyber threats.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	UC-related KPIs: KPI-5.
Risks (THREATS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Envisions unauthorised access to the 6G Infrastructure through privilege abuse by an inside actor and an outside actor by exploiting software vulnerabilities or erroneous configurations in the 6G Facility infrastructures. • Information Gathering about Services and Devices communicating through the Internet. • Abnormal Traffic / Distributed Denial of Service attack targeting System Components.
UC integration	
UC name	UC3 - Utilities Management and Security.
Integration description	As mobile network and cloud adoption gain momentum in the utility sector, the utility manager needs to understand network and cloud migration's security and compliance implications.
Integration objectives	Objective 4: Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, decision, and Mitigation Strategies.

	This objective will enable the detection of anomalies as well as determine response actions to achieve optimised mitigation results at the radio layer and the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, detecting not only known threats but also unknown (0-day) vulnerabilities to occur in complex cross-vertical layer, cross-domain, and cross-network segment layers.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	UC-related KPIs: Availability of the system.
Risks (THREATS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Security – Unauthorized access. • Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks. • Code and data injection attacks.
UC integration	
UC name	UC4 - PPDR IoT Situational Awareness platform.
Integration description	PPDR scenarios involve challenging (and real-time) coordination between teams on the field and Command-and-Control Centre (CCC) operators in rough environments.
Integration objectives	Objective 4: Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Risk Assessment and Mitigation Strategies - AI-driven anomaly detection and mitigation detection strategies fulfil the increasing need for autonomous (or semi-autonomous) mechanisms capable of processing large and complex amounts of data (e.g., network communications, video streams) and timely detect deviations and proactively assist their resolution.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	UC-related KPIs: KPI-5, KPI-14, & KPI-30.
Risks (THREATS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPDR scene and team provisioning. • Intrusion into the system to access privileged information or cause disruption of services. • Disclosure of device vulnerability or unlawful appropriation of a device.

Table 62 - Threat Risk Assessor: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	N/A
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Contingent to the existence of the AID, TRA will function as its co-processor.
Goals	
KPIs/KVIs	
Risks	

Table 63 presents the roadmap for the Threat Risk Assessor asset.

Table 63 - Threat Risk Assessor: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Architectural Design & Technical specification	M3-M27	T2.3
Development specification for TRA	M4-M30	T4.3
Plans for the prototype integration activities	M6-M30	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
In-lab Testing	M12-M34	T5.2

3.3.22.R20: Network Security Flow Monitoring

Table 64 presents the integration details between the Network Security Flow Monitoring asset and the UC1.

Table 64 - Network Security Flow Monitoring: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	One of the main achievements to be obtained with the development of the 6G technologies is the capability of threat detection within the multiple overlay network and technologies that coexist alongside the entire 5G/6G topology infrastructure. Here is where the Network Security Monitoring Agent takes place, detecting specific and known attacks, such as DDoS orchestrated in a botnet. This asset provides the detection of the incoming threat, additionally to fine grain metadata about the malicious flow detected with its next-generation network encapsulation, due to some advanced networking protocols such as VXLAN, GRE or GTP that enable some features of the 6G systems like multi-tenancy and user mobility.
Integration objectives	Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation Strategies
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA. KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1 minute).
Risks	RM1: Inadequate management. RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase. RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations. RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget. RT2: Lack of integration among tools. RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation. RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components. RT9: Integration of developed components.

	RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.
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Table 65 details the testbed deployment of the Network Security Flow Monitoring asset at ORO's testbed.

Table 65 - Network Security Flow Monitoring: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	To validate the NSFM capabilities in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. To evaluate the performance of the NSFM and validate its KPIs in a real 5G/6G infrastructure.
Goals	To deploy and integrate a functional asset with detection capabilities of cyber-attacks, in addition to the provision of the fine-grain metadata of the malicious flow detected. Therefore, integration with the other assets of the RIGOUROUS framework is necessary to close the SOAR cognitive loop that the UWS provides to the framework.
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA. KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1 minute).
Risks	RM1: Inadequate management. RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase. RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations. RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget. RT2: Lack of integration among tools. RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation. RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components. RT9: Integration of developed components. RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.

Table 65 presents the roadmap for the Network Security Flow Monitoring asset.

Table 66 - Network Security Flow Monitoring: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Map and description with requirements	M5	M4.4
Literature review	M5	M4.4
Design and sequence diagrams	M7	M4.4

Description of cyber-attacks	M8	M4.4
Design of the attack (selection of tool + configuration of botnet)	M12	M4.4
Configuration of the traditional IDS	M13	M4.4
Implementation of the overlay network recorder	M15	M4.4
Implementation of the alert interface	M15	M4.4
Asset functional validation	M16	M4.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
First integration design iteration	M18	M4.4
Integration process	M23	M4.4
Empirical results: full test bed setup	M26	M4.4
Empirical results: validation	M28	M4.4
Empirical results: evaluation	M30	M4.4

3.3.23.R20: Slice Mitigation Planner Service

Table 67 presents the integration details between the Slice Mitigation Planner Service asset and UC1.

Table 67 - Slice Mitigation Planner Service: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	<p>Time is crucial in planning the mitigation of cyber threats, especially in networks with constantly changing topologies. Engineers require significant intervention. As the network's complexity grows, so does the difficulty of devising a final mitigation plan. Therefore, prescriptive analytics for systems like 5G/6G network topologies are essential for minimizing human intervention in decision-making for mitigation plans.</p> <p>This is where the SMPS steps in, providing the RIGOUROUS framework with a set of decisions to mitigate incoming threats through the publication of this information via the specified communication exchange interface. It offers vital information such as where to stop the attack, how to stop it when to stop it, and for how long the attack should be halted. This information is derived from advanced planning rules that combine topological information from the TIA with malicious flow information from the NSMA.</p>
Integration objectives	Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation Strategies
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA.</p> <p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1 minute).</p>
Risks	<p>RM1: Inadequate management.</p> <p>RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.</p>

	<p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation.</p> <p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>
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Table 68 details the testbed deployment of the Slice Mitigation Planner Service asset at ORO's testbed.

Table 68 - Slice Mitigation Planner Service: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	To validate the SMPS capabilities in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. To evaluate the performance of the SMPS and validate its KPIs in a real 5G/6G infrastructure.
Goals	To deploy and integrate a functional asset with planning capabilities to mitigate incoming cyber-attacks. Therefore, integration with the other assets of the RIGUROUS framework is necessary to close the SOAR cognitive loop that the UWS provides to the framework.
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA. KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGUROUS: <1 minute).
Risks	<p>RM1: Inadequate management.</p> <p>RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation.</p> <p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>

Table 69 presents the roadmap for the Slice Mitigation Planner asset.

Table 69 - Slice Mitigation Planner Service: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Map and description with requirements	M5	T4.4
Literature review	M7	T4.4
Design and sequence diagrams	M10	T4.4
Implementation of the PA rule model	M13	T4.4
Design model of topology database	M14	T4.4
Creation of E2E path algorithm	M15	T4.4
Asset functional validation	M16	T4.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
First integration design iteration	M18	T4.4
Integration process	M23	T4.4
Empirical results: Full testbed setup	M26	T4.4
Empirical results: Validation	M28	T4.4
Empirical results: Evaluation	M30	T4.4

3.3.24.R20: Topology Inventory Agent

Table 70 presents the integration details between the Topology Inventory Agent asset and UC1.

Table 70 - Topology Inventory Agent: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats
Integration description	6G topology infrastructures are continuously changing and evolving. New systems, devices and technologies are being integrated, and those changes directly affect the decisions that the engineers make to mitigate an incoming threat. Hence, it's crucial to have a clear and real-time overview of the network topology, hence proactive (but also reactive) measures can be taken. This asset provides the RIGOUROUS framework with a real-time view of the network topology, concerning computers, devices, containers, technologies and more information needed to create a proper decision in the mitigation process of an attack.
Integration objectives	Advanced AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation Strategies
Specific KPIs/KVIs	KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA. KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1 minute).
Risks	RM1: Inadequate management. RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication. RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.

	<p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation.</p> <p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>
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Table 71 details the testbed deployment of the Topology Inventory Agent asset at ORO's testbed.

Table 71 - Topology Inventory Agent: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	To validate the TIA capabilities in a real 5G/6G infrastructure. To evaluate the performance of the TIA and validate its KPIs in a real 5G/6G infrastructure
Goals	To deploy and integrate a functional asset with topology monitoring capabilities, thus providing with 5G/6G system's topology overview to the RIGOUROUS framework. Therefore, integration with the other assets of the RIGOUROUS framework is necessary to close the SOAR cognitive loop that the UWS provides to the framework.
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-20: Decrease mitigation reaction time by 50% compared to SOTA. KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1 minute).
Risks	<p>RM1: Inadequate management.</p> <p>RM2: Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>RM3: Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>RM4: A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations.</p> <p>RM5: Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>RT2: Lack of integration among tools.</p> <p>RT3: Insufficient equipment and facilities to perform tests and validation.</p> <p>RT7: Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify an appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>RT9: Integration of developed components.</p> <p>RT13: Results in the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated.</p>

Table 72 presents the roadmap for the Topology Inventory Agent asset.

Table 72 - Topology Inventory Agent: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Map and description with requirements	M5	T4.4
Literature review	M7	T4.4
Design and sequence diagrams	M10	T4.4
Description of technologies to be monitored	M12	T4.4
Creation of the Topology Model	M13	T4.4
Implementation of the Topology Database	M14	T4.4
Implementation of the Topology Sender	M15	T4.4
Asset functional validation	M16	T4.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
First integration design iteration	M18	T4.4
Integration process	M23	T4.4
Empirical results: full test bed setup	M26	T4.4
Empirical results: validation	M28	T4.4
Empirical results: evaluation	M30	T4.4

3.3.25.R21: Encryption as a Service

Table 73 presents the integration details between the Encryption as a Service asset and UC4.

Table 73 - Encryption as a Service: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	Integrating Homomorphic Encryption (HE) enhances privacy and data confidentiality. HE enables secure data sharing by encrypting and decrypting local model parameters. Oulu is in charge of HE and will investigate how to leverage it within the Encryption as a Service (EaaS) asset of ICTFI.
Integration objectives	Integrating HE to enhance privacy and data confidentiality through the facilitation of secure data sharing. Validate the integration between the HSPF and the RIGOUROUS Security Analytics Engine (SAE) component, using a RIGOUROUS UC
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving System scalability by more than 7% Key Generation Time is crucial for efficient encryption or decryption. We aim to improve it by more than 7%. Establishing benchmarks for CPU and RAM usage levels optimizes resource utilization for encryption and decryption instances. We aim to improve CPU and RAM usage by more than 10%. Service Scalability Efficiency (SSE) is a KVI that measures the ratio of achieved scalability to the target scalability for encryption and decryption. A higher percentage indicates efficient scalability. We aim to improve SSE by 10%.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimizing CPU and RAM usage for encryption/decryption instances to improve resource utilization efficiency by more than 10%.
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delay with integration with OULU (HE) and ICTIFI (EaaS) The integration with the UC4 and EaaS components has been experiencing delays Maintaining the availability is challenging Delays in the integration with the RIGOUROUS SAE component

Table 74 details the testbed deployment of the Encryption as a Service asset at the ICTFI testbed.

Table 74 - Encryption as a Service: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ICTFI
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Integration and validation of the asset's components with UC4
Goals	Integrate this Asset with UC4 and apply it to specific data of UC4
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-31: After accessing the API, the stakeholders can be served with cryptography services provided by ICTFI testbed, and then they can express their quality of experience.</p> <p>KPI-32: The industrial environments requiring cryptography services can use the API to connect to the framework and use the services.</p>
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulties with remote access to the testbed Launching real-world attacks against data confidentiality to test data leakage is challenging High bandwidth consumption of centre components such as request handler Identified the data of UC4 that would need both EaaS and HE.

Table 75 presents the roadmap for the Encryption as a Service asset.

Table 75 - Encryption as a Service: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial integration of HE within EaaS	M18	T5.1
Second prototype		
Initial evaluation of HE and EaaS to UC4	M24	T5.2

3.3.26.R22: Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management

Table 76 presents the integration details between the Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management asset and UC4.

Table 76 - Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC4
Integration description	In the case of a PPDR event, it is necessary to provision a network with the required services for the task. These services must be resilient against adversarial actions, with varying defense budgets according to the criticality of the service and the current cyber threat landscape. The asset herein integrated will provide network-bounded seamless movement across the exploration space (i.e., a Moving Target Defense (MTD) approach).
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow for describing the exploration space per service/virtual link/virtual unit. • Observe effective movement over the exploration space without disruption to the services. • Demonstrate the asset is effective against the threats to the UC.
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-3: contribute to providing additional types of supported security models.</p> <p>KPI-12: the MTD approach should help reduce the number of false positives when used in conjunction with previous detection methods.</p> <p>KPI-13: the added authenticated access data should help increase anomaly detection.</p> <p>KPI-14: (potentially) contributes to reducing time to detection by generating a more direct event for failing to hit the target.</p> <p>KPI-15: detect unknown threats/scenarios. As per the MTD definition, it is just as effective against zero-day threats as already-known threats.</p> <p>KPI-19: implicit authentication may reduce the scale-up operations if the threat is not a valid user (probably ineffective otherwise).</p> <p>KPI-20: reduce the mitigation reaction time by having faster event reporting, as in KPI-14.</p> <p>KPI-22: reduce mitigation time by having an easily pluggable mechanism that provides quick remediation (at least until the root issue(s) are resolved).</p> <p>KPI-23: reduce the early-stage security threat warning time by having faster event reporting, as in KPI-14.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology</p>

	<p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components</p> <p>R14 - RIGOUROUS applications and services result in slow performance, failing to operate in real-time</p>
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Table 77 details the testbed deployment of the Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management asset at ONE's testbed.

Table 77 - Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	OneSource testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	PPDR scenarios demand critical communications and coping with highly dynamic evolving situations. The cause for that PPDR event may be of various natures, including adversarial action by a powerful attacker. To that end, the integrated MTD asset should be able to cope with the exploitation of unknown vulnerabilities while minimizing the potential disruption caused by the defense.
Goals	Successfully validate the asset in a realistic PPDR scenario.
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-3: contribute to providing additional types of supported security models.</p> <p>KPI-12: the MTD approach should help reduce the number of false positives when used in conjunction with previous detection methods.</p> <p>KPI-13: the added authenticated access data should help increase anomaly detection.</p> <p>KPI-14: (potentially) contributes to reducing time to detection by generating a more direct event for failing to hit the target.</p> <p>KPI-15: detect unknown threats/scenarios. As per the MTD definition, it is just as effective against zero-day threats as already-known threats.</p> <p>KPI-19: implicit authentication may reduce the scale-up operations if the threat is not a valid user (probably ineffective otherwise).</p> <p>KPI-20: reduce the mitigation reaction time by having faster event reporting, as in KPI-14.</p> <p>KPI-22: reduce mitigation time by having an easily pluggable mechanism that provides quick remediation (at least until the root issue(s) are resolved).</p> <p>KPI-23: reduce the early-stage security threat warning time by having faster event reporting, as in KPI-14.</p>
Risks	<p>R1 - Inadequate management</p> <p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving consortium in a critical phase</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology</p>

	<p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components</p> <p>R14 - RIGOUROUS applications and services result in slow performance, failing to operate in real-time</p>
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Table 78 presents the roadmap for the Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management asset.

Table 78 - Network-based MTD modelling and specification for DevSecOps and risk management: Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial specification of network services in terms of mutation	M16	T3.1
Specification and validation of the mutation policies	M18	T3.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Testing and validation with UC4	M24	T5.1

3.3.27.R23: Privacy-preserving CTI sharing

Table 79 presents the integration details between the Privacy-preserving CTI sharing asset and UC1.

Table 79 - Privacy preserving CTI sharing: Integration with UCs.

UC integration	
UC name	UC1 (ORO)
Integration description	The information generated from any of the scenarios in the Use Case will be anonymized (if necessary) and transmitted through MISP using this asset.
Integration objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be able to receive the information as Indicators of Compromise (IoCs), and the privacy policies to be applied, using the asset's defined interfaces Be able to anonymize the received events according to the privacy policies previously defined Be able to, once anonymized, publish the event in the local MISP instance <p>Synchronize, at least, 2 MISP instances to check that the information is being shared as expected</p>
Specific KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1min)</p> <p>KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases including conditions based real operational environments</p>
Risks	<p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology.</p>

	<p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>R19 - Results if the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated</p>
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Table 80 details the testbed deployment of the Privacy-preserving CTI sharing at the ONE testbed.

Table 80 - Privacy preserving CTI sharing: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	UMU Testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Share CTI information in a privacy-preserving manner using PET technologies
Goals	<p>Privacy Preserving Cyber Threat Intelligence Sharing module is oriented to anonymize sensitive information present in cyber threat reports and does it by hiding attributes that discloses identity of a certain entity. The way in which that personal information is hidden is defined by the privacy policies customized by the organization that's sharing the information.</p> <p>Data mining techniques such as suppression, generalization, K-Anonymity, T-Closeness, L-Diversity and Differential Privacy are available in this asset.</p> <p>This asset will connect with MISP organization's instance, which also is connected to other organization's instances by the synchronization process, creating a MISP network where different organizations are interconnected sharing threat information about attacks received, new vulnerabilities discovered and any threat alert or any usefull cybersecurity information. This information could be used to prevent a future cyber attack.</p>
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1min)</p> <p>KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases including conditions based real operational environments</p>
Risks	<p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology.</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy</p>
Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO Testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration with all the scenarios in UC1
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication of anonymized threat events from real information generated from RIGOUROUS assets involved in this testbed/use case.

KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-22: Target mitigation time against cyber-attacks, including all the stages of the complete SOAR cognitive loop (SOTA: 480 minutes; RIGOUROUS: <1min)</p> <p>KPI-30: Demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases including conditions based real operational environments</p>
Risks	<p>R2 - Partners are not reacting as expected or lack communication.</p> <p>R3 - Partners leaving Consortium in a critical phase.</p> <p>R5 - Deviations affecting schedule or budget.</p> <p>R6 - A new wave of infectious disease or pandemic.</p> <p>R7 - Gaps between needs and developed technology.</p> <p>R13 - Difficulty of runtime adaptation framework to identify appropriate solution to resolve component interoperability/security/trust/privacy issues through reconfiguration of components.</p> <p>R19 - Results if the different WPs are not compatible (functionally or technologically) and therefore cannot be integrated</p>

Table 81 presents the roadmap for the Privacy-preserving CTI sharing asset.

Table 81 - Privacy preserving CTI sharing: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Prototype	M24	T4.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Working version of the asset being able to anonymize the IoC generated from the DDoS that will take place in UC4	M30	T4.1

3.4. Mapping of UCs to Testbeds and Roadmap

This section presents the mapping of UCs to testbeds. This section also encompasses several sub-sections that details each integration between UCs and Testbeds and presents its correspondent roadmap.

Table 82 presents the mapping of UCs to Testbeds.

Table 82 – Mapping of UCs to Testbeds.

#	UC	UMU	ORO	EBOS	WINGS	OULU	ONE	ICTFI
UC1	Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats		x					
UC2	Digital City Twining Platform							x
UC3	Utilities Management and Security				x			
UC4	PPDR IoT Situational Awareness Platform	x	x				x	

3.4.1. UC1: Protection of 6G-enabled Services against Cyber Threats

Table 83 presents the testbed deployment of the UC1 at ORO's testbed.

Table 83 - UC1: Testbeds Deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO Testbed
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of RIGOUROUS Components • Achieve successful integration of RIGOUROUS components • Validate deployment and functionality of the RIGOUROUS Framework components in an relevant operational scenario
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of UC1 • Integration of Assets (R1, R2, R4, R5, R7, R8, R11, R12, R16, R19, R20, R23)
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assets are not available for integration • Deployment is delayed due to integration issues in UC1 scenarios • Testbed remote access issues
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-6: ORO's UC1 demonstration will make use of A.I.-enabled orchestration of at minimum 4 resource types, namely Virtual Network Functions, Physical Network Functions, Services and Devices</p> <p>KPI-22: ORO Testbed will provide a performant testing and experimentation facility, to demonstrate a reduction in the target mitigation time against cyber-threats across all stages of the cognitive-SOAR, compared to SOTA (480 minutes)</p> <p>KPI-23: The planned UC demonstrator will test and validate Early-Stage Threat Warning optimisation of at minimum, 15 minutes compared to SoTA (Elastic Security Deployment)</p> <p>KPI-30: ORO Testbed will support the demonstration of the RIGOUROUS main innovations in the four key use cases using conditions based real operational environments, by developing and supporting one UC</p>

Table 84 presents the roadmap for UC1.

Table 84 - UC1: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial deployment - ORO Testbed	M12	T5.1
Initial integration of assets R20, R11	M16	T5.1, T4.4, T3.4
Initial integration of assets R05, R08	M16	T3.1, T3.3
Initial integration of assets R07, R12, R23, R01, R02, R04	M16	T4.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Preliminary integration of assets R01, R02, R04, R07, R12, R23	M19	T4.1
Preliminary integration of assets R05, R08	M19	T3.1, T3.3
Preliminary integration of R11, R20	M19	T4.4, T5.1
Testing, validation and final integration of assets with UC1	M22	T5.1

Testing, validation of assets R01, R02, R04, R07, R12, R23 with UC1	M22	T5.1
Testing, validation of assets R05, R08 with UC1	M22	T5.1
Testing, validation of assets R11, R20 with UC1	M22	T5.1
Testing and KPI collection with UC1	M24	T5.1
Demonstration in realistic, business-relevant scenarios for UC1	M34	T5.3
Final report on integration, testing and validation	M36	T5.3

3.4.2. UC2: Digital City Twining Platform

Table 85 presents the testbed deployment of the UC2 at ICTFI's testbed.

Table 85 - UC2: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ICTFI
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate deployment • Validation of UC2 <p>This use case focuses on ensuring secure communication between the IoT gateways and the Microservices in the platform's backend, which may be located either at the edge or in the cloud. The objective is to prevent privacy violations by safeguarding the data. Additionally, it addresses integrating and validating the asset's components with UC2.</p>
Goals	Integrate the Assets of UC2 with the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset of Oulu
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties with remote access to the testbed • Low Testbed resources
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-21: Data leakage has to be prevented with a high performance in the EaaS framework, as it is designed to provide security for other sectors.</p> <p>KPI-29: The EaaS framework is designed to facilitate the cryptographic processes, especially for resource-limited devices. This framework has to provide adequate algorithms to orchestrate the cryptographic processes required for handling end-users' requests.</p>

Table 86 presents the roadmap for UC2.

Table 86 - UC2: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Design of the main components algorithms	M18	T5.1
Securing the service mesh	M19	T5.1
Second prototype	Month	Task
Testing and validation of the security mechanism for the service mesh	M24	T5.1

3.4.3. UC3: Utilities Management and security

Table 87 presents the testbed deployment of the UC3 at WINGS's testbed.

Table 87 - UC3: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	WINGS
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	Validation of UC3 Integration of assets based on RIGOUROUS architecture
Goals	Successful integration of all assets used in UC3
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of baseline data to train required models and provide measurable outcomes Delays on the integration of different assets
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-29: Regular testing and validation to be ready for real world demonstrations</p> <p>KPI-30: The implementation of UC3 at WINGS testbed will allow the demonstration in real-world operational settings and the integration with the rest of the RIGOUROUS framework.</p>

Table 88 presents the roadmap for UC3.

Table 88 - UC3: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Preliminary integration with Cyber-Physical Correlator and DASC	M16	T4.2, T4.3
Second prototype	Month	Task
Stable version integrated with Cyber-Physical Correlator and DASC	M20	T4.2, T4.3
Testing and validation of integrations with Cyber-Physical Correlator and DASC	M22	T5.1

3.4.4. UC4: PPDR IoT Situational Awareness platform

Table 89 presents the testbed deployment of UC4 at ONE and UMU testbeds.

Table 89 - UC4: Testbeds deployment.

Testbed	
Testbed name	ONE
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<p>List of objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validate deployment Explore the use of PVCs by the different micro-services (to maintain history of past operations) Integrations with Assets (Namely, R12, R21 and R22)
Goals	List of goals:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of UC4 • Achieve successful integrations with Assets (R21, R22)
Risks	<p>List of risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PVCs are not available • Delay on the integrations with the identified Assets
KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI-24: The envisioned integrations will be conducted in a way to expedite the integration process, by starting with partner-to-partner discussions, followed by preliminary integrations in controlled scenarios, respective testing, and validation, and only then moving into complex environments, namely, to the integration with the RIGOUROUS framework. Moreover, all the identified integrations will have a dedicated bi-weekly meeting to keep track on the integration status and dedicated integration sessions will be schedule whenever they are required.</p> <p>KPI-29: Although the UC4 has already achieved a mature development status, it is subject to continuous development activities. As such, its continuous testing and validation in Kubernetes ensures its readiness for demonstration activities.</p>
Testbed	
Testbed name	UMU
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of the UC4 with the RIGOUROUS framework • Ensure connectivity between the UC4 BKs and the 5G infrastructure
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate the UC with the RIGOUROUS framework
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties with the remote access to the testbed • Delays and issues while integrating the RIGOUROUS framework with UC4
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-24 and KPI-29, as stated before
Testbed	
Testbed name	ORO
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration with Assets focused on the 5G connectivity (i.e., slicing mechanism, etc)
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate the UC4 UEs with the Assets focused on the 5G connectivity
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties with the remote access to the testbed • Delays and issues while integrating the chosen Assets with UC4
KPIs/KVIs	KPI-24 and KPI-29, as stated before

Table 90 presents the roadmap for UC4.

Table 90 - UC4: Integration Roadmap.

First prototype	Month	Task
Initial deployment at ONE	M12	T5.1

Initial integration with Asset R12 (Holistic Security and Privacy Framework)	M13	T4.1
Initial deployment at UMU	M14	T5.1
Preliminary integration with Asset R01, R07 at UMU	M14	T5.1
Preliminary integration with Asset R21 at ONE	M14	T4.4
Preliminary integration with Asset R03, R04 and R22 at ONE	M14	T3.1
Initial deployment at ORO	M15	T5.1
Preliminary integration with Asset R11 and R15 at ORO	M16	T3.4
Second prototype	Month	Task
Preliminary integration with UC2	M17	T5.1
Preliminary integration with Assets R09 and R10 at UMU	M17	T3.2
Preliminary integration with Assets R16, R17 and R19 at UMU	M18	T4.3
Preliminary integration with Assets R13, R14 at ONE	M19	T4.1
Preliminary integration with Asset R12 (Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector)	M19	T4.1
Testing and validation of integrations with Assets R03, R04, R21 and R22	M20	T5.1
Preliminary integration with Asset R12 (Privacy-preserving Federated AI for anomaly detection)	M21	T4.1
Testing and validation of integration with UC2	M22	T5.1
Testing and validation of integrations with Assets R01 and R07	M22	T5.1
Testing and validation of integrations with Asset R11 and R15	M23	T5.1
Testing, validation and KPIs collection of the integration with the three R12 Assets	M24	T5.1

4 IN-LAB TESTING

The following section provides a first report on the initial outcomes of T5.2 InLab Testing, that spans the period from M12 to M34 of the project. The task will focus on evaluating the RIGOUROUS integrated prototype in a lab-based environment before rolling out the use cases in trials. Initially, the prototype will be validated in a state-of-the-art 5G/IoT testbed, where various types of cyber threats will be considered and tested to identify any system vulnerabilities and ensure the robustness and trustworthiness of the developed system before real-life trials. Additionally, these lab tests will provide initial quantitative feedback on the performance of the modules, such as response time, accuracy of threat identification, threat categorization, and the quality of AI-based decisions regarding appropriate mitigation measures based on threat classifications and overall network conditions. This lab-based testing will be conducted in two cycles (the first up to M24 and the second up to M30), providing feedback to WP2, WP3, and WP4 for further improvements on the developed modules and prototype integration.

The main results of T5.2 In-Lab testing will be reported in upcoming deliverables D5.2 and D5.3 on M24 and M36 respectively.

4.1. Methodology

From a methodology perspective In-lab testing of the integrated prototype will be split in two phases/iterations as mentioned before and approached gradually at different levels as follows:

- **Unit testing of the individual RIGOUROUS modules:** This is a software testing methodology that focuses on verifying the functionality of individual units or components, such as functions or methods, in isolation from the rest of the application. This approach ensures that each unit performs correctly by automating tests, which can be repeated consistently to detect regressions and bugs early in the development process. Unit tests, often automated using frameworks like Junit, unit test or NUnit, serve as documentation and facilitate refactoring by ensuring code changes do not break existing functionality. The primary benefits include early bug detection, improved code quality, and enhanced software stability.
- **Integration testing of adjacent modules in the RIGOUROUS architecture:** This is a software testing type where individual units or components are combined and tested as a group to ensure they function together correctly. This testing focuses on verifying the interactions and interfaces between units, identifying defects in their integration. Integration testing can be done using various approaches, such as Big Bang, Incremental (including top-down and bottom-up), and Sandwich (hybrid) integration testing. By using stubs and drivers to simulate incomplete parts of the application, integration tests help uncover issues early, enhance test coverage, and ensure the reliability of the software's combined components before progressing to system testing.
- **System testing of the RIGOUROUS integrated prototype:** This type of testing is a crucial phase in software development where the entire integrated system is evaluated to ensure that it meets specified requirements and functions correctly within its intended environment. This process involves testing the system as a whole, examining its interactions

with external systems, assessing its performance, and verifying its compliance with both functional and non-functional requirements. System testing aims to uncover defects that may arise from the integration of different components and to validate that the system behaves as expected, ultimately ensuring its reliability, functionality, and quality before deployment.

- **Functional testing of the RIGOUROUS modules and the integrated prototype as a whole:** This is a type of software testing that evaluates the functionality of a system or application by testing its features against specified requirements. This testing process aims to verify that the software behaves as expected, performs its intended functions correctly, and meets the user's needs. Functional testing focuses on validating the behaviour of the software's individual functions or features, such as user interface interactions, data manipulation, calculations, and integrations with other systems. It involves designing test cases based on functional specifications, executing those test cases, comparing actual results with expected results, and identifying any discrepancies or defects. Functional testing helps ensure the reliability, usability, and compliance of the software with functional requirements before it is released to users.
- **Non-functional testing of the RIGOUROUS modules and the integrated prototype as a whole:** Non-functional testing is a type of software testing that evaluates the characteristics of a system beyond its specific functional requirements. Instead of focusing on what the system does, non-functional testing assesses how well it performs in terms of attributes such as scalability, reliability, performance, usability, security, and compatibility. This testing process aims to verify that the software meets the quality standards and requirements related to these non-functional aspects, ensuring a satisfactory user experience and adherence to organizational standards. Non-functional testing involves designing test cases to measure and evaluate these attributes, executing tests under different conditions, analysing the results, and identifying any areas where the system may not meet expectations. By conducting non-functional testing, organizations can mitigate risks, optimize system performance, and enhance the overall quality of the software product.

As T5.2 proceeds, along with the development of the different modules and elicitation of the integration requirements, such tests shall be specified in detail. Furthermore, depending on the integration and tests requirements the appropriate testbeds shall be selected based on their capabilities, for the corresponding tests to be run.

4.2. Tests Planning

During the first T5.2 period (M12-M18), as the partners are finalizing the development of the different RIGOUROUS modules and the integration requirements are still being specified in parallel, limited In-lab testing was performed or planned. Specifically, a number of unit tests or limited scale integration tests were collected in the following template (See Table 91).

Table 91 – Initial Period Tests Template.

Information on Tests Performed and planned to be performed per Asset
--

#	Asset(s) name	Partner(s) involved	Test description	Planned or already Performed	Testbed(s) involved	Test expected results	Test actual results	Comments and references

A sample of the tests collected can be found in Annex V: InLab Testing – Initial Period Tests.

For the next period of In-lab testing (M18–M24) a much more thorough testing plan is foreseen that will include all types of tests. To this end the template in Table 92 below has been prepared and will be utilized to record the test cases. The context of the test cases will be provided by the different UC descriptions and corresponding Threat Scenarios as presented in D2.2 RIGOUROUS Use Cases [3] and hence the table columns labels. Thus, for each threat scenario a cluster of relevant assets involved will be tested utilizing different respective test cases that will be recorder accordingly in Table 92. The test case descriptions should at least address the following:

- Input data needed from testbed or other assets
- Testbed or other assets integration needed
- Expected output data
- Interface on which output data will be communicated
- Expected response/results
- Expected performance
- Other parameters to be measured and expected values
- Relevant KPIs

The test cases should also include “unexpected” instances too if possible, such as false positive anomaly detections or anomalies “unknown” to RIGOUROUS.

Table 92 - Inlab Testing - Test Cases Template.

Assets Name	UC1		
	Threat Scenario 1: Unauthorized access	Threat Scenario 2: Information Gathering about Services and Devices communicating through the Internet	Threat Scenario 3: A service exposed through an EDGE component of ORO 6G Facility is targeted and attacked
Assets Name	UC2		
	Threat Scenario 1: Unlawful access to IoT gateways, platform’s APIs, and IoT data violating data privacy	Threat Scenario 2: Unauthorized communications to micro-services of an IoT smart city platform	Threat Scenario 3: Economical Denial of Service and Adversary AI attacks

Assets Name	UC3			
	Threat Scenario 1: Data Security - Unauthorized Access	Threat Scenario 2: Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks	Threat Scenario 3: Code and data injection attacks	Threat Scenario 4: Outdated systems
Assets Name	UC4			
	Threat Scenario 1: PPDR scene and teams provisioning	Threat Scenario 2: Intrusion into system to access privileged information or cause disruption of services	Threat Scenario 3: Disclosure of device vulnerability or unlawful appropriation of a device	

4.3. Time Plan

The time plan regarding In-lab testing actions for the next 12 months, up to M30 which includes MS6 (In-Lab RIGOUROUS integrated framework assessment) on M24 and covers the two cycles of In-Lab testing (first up to M24 and second up to M30), is provided in the Gantt Chart in Table 93 below.

Table 93 - Inlab Testing Gantt Chart

Actions	M 1 9	M 2 0	M 2 1	M 2 2	M 2 3	M 2 4	M 2 5	M 2 6	M 2 7	M 2 8	M 2 9	M 3 0
Finalization of assets initial development												
Test cases development												
Test beds preparation												
RIGOUROUS asset cluster installations and testbed integrations												
First cycle of tests												
Reports on first In-Lab test results and feedback to asset owners and T5.3												
Adaptations to assets based on test feedback												
Adaptations to test cases for 2nd cycle of In-Lab testing												
Adaptations to test beds based on feedback												

5 CONCLUSIONS

All development processes involving a wide array of components encounter significant challenges in establishing effective integrations among them. To address this, a well-defined and structured integration plan is essential. This document outlines the integration plan crucial for the successful implementation of the RIGOUROUS framework.

The document begins by detailing the integration methodology for integrating the different RIGOUROUS components, properly accompanied with a high-level Roadmap. The project common tools are also presented, as well as the interfaces template which enabled a standardize definition of the different project points of integration.

Moreover, the integration strategy has been presented, namely with the presentation of all the mappings required between the RIGOUROUS architecture Functional Blocks and Assets, Assets and UCs, and Testbeds and even UCs and Testbeds. A detailed description has been provided for each integration/deployment, as well as a roadmap detailing the different steps for the different activities.

The In-Lab testing methodology, test planning and foreseen roadmap are also described.

In conclusion, this document provides essential guidance for the ongoing integration activities in WP5, outlining how different integrations should proceed in the future. Given the evolving nature of the RIGOUROUS components, an updated version of this information will be included in D5.2, scheduled for release by M24.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] ONLYOFFICE, [HTTPS://WWW.ONLYOFFICE.COM/](https://www.onlyoffice.com/), accessed at: 2024-06-03
- [2] GitLab, [HTTPS://ABOUT.GITLAB.COM/](https://about.gitlab.com/), accessed at: 2024-06-03
- [3] Deliverable 2.2 - RIGOUROUS Use-Cases

ANNEX I: ASSETS TEMPLATE

Generic Information

Generic Information	
Asset number	
Asset name	
Responsible partner	
Other partners	
Will an asset first version be ready for M16 integration?	Yes/No
Will an asset first version be ready for MS5 (M18)?	Yes/No
Will it be integrated with RIGOUROUS framework?	Yes/No
Will it be integrated with use cases?	Yes/No
Will it be deployed in testbeds?	Yes/No

Use case integration

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned Asset/UC integration.

UC integration	
UC name	
Integration description	
Integration objectives	
Specific KPIs/KVIs	
Risks	

UC integration	
UC name	
Integration description	
Integration objectives	
Specific KPIs/KVIs	
Risks	

Testbeds deployment

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned Asset/Testbed integration.

Testbed	
Testbed name	

Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	
Goals	
KPIs/KVIs	
Risks	

Testbed	
Testbed name	
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	
Goals	
KPIs/KVIs	
Risks	

Interfaces List

List all the Asset interfaces.

Target Component	Responsible partner	Implementation Status	Observations
		Not started/Initiated Development/ Validated/Final	(Complementary information)

Roadmap

First prototype	Month	Task

Second prototype	Month	Task

Mapping with project KPIs/KVIs for UC Integrations

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned Asset/UC integration.

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Mapping with project KPIs/KVIs for Testbeds Integrations

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned Asset/Testbed integration.

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Other information

Add any information you consider relevant to the asset integration activities.

ANNEX II: UCs TEMPLATE

Generic Information

Generic Information	
UC number	
UC name	
Responsible partner	
Will a UC first version be ready for M16 integration?	Yes/No
Will a UC version (ideally, stable) be ready for M18?	Yes/No
Will it be integrated with RIGOUROUS framework?	Yes/No
Will it be integrated with Assets?	Yes/No
Will it be deployed in testbeds?	Yes/No

Testbeds deployment

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned UC/Testbed integration.

Testbed	
Testbed name	
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	
Goals	
Risks	

Testbed	
Testbed name	
Objectives (justify testbed deployment)	
Goals	
Risks	

Mapping with project KPIs/KVIs

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned UC/Testbed integration.

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Project KPI/KVI	Description
-----------------	-------------

Roadmap

First prototype	Month	Task

Second prototype	Month	Task

Other information

Add any information you consider relevant to the UC integration activities.

ANNEX III: TESTBEDS TEMPLATE

Generic Information

Generic Information	
Testbed number	
Testbed name	
Testbed location	
Responsible partner	
Testbed with 5G	Yes/No
Cloud Infrastructure without 5G	Yes/No
Provides remote access	Yes/No
Provides a Kubernetes environment	Yes/No
Will this testbed be available to support integrations by M16?	Yes/No
Will this testbed be available to support integrations by M18?	Yes/No
Will it be integrated with RIGOUROUS framework?	Yes/No

Characteristics

Topic	Observation
5G coverage	NA/indoor/outdoor
Complementary information about 5G Infrastructure	
Complementary information about support Infrastructure (i.e., Kubernetes, others)	
Remote Access	
<i>Any other relevant topic</i>	

Innovations

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the Innovations the testbed will provide/support.

Innovations data	
Innovation name	
Innovation description	
Objectives	
Goals	

Innovations data	
Innovation name	
Innovation description	
Objectives	
Goals	

Mapping with project KPIs/KVIs

Fill one or more tables with the identification of the planned testbed innovations and testbed integrations.

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Project KPI/KVI	Description

Other information

Add any information you consider relevant to the testbed integration activities.

ANNEX IV: INTERFACES DEFINITION

EDoS Mitigator – Data Monitoring (Metrics Collector)

Field	Description
Interface code	EDoS_DM
Status	development
Component #1	Data Monitoring (Metrics Collector)
Component #2	EDoS Mitigator
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Get resource usage and service performance metrics of the service that EDoS Mitigator is protecting against EDoS attacks as a CSV file.
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/api/v1/get_k8s_metrics_csv
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	<pre>{ "namespace": "string", "deployment": "string", "pod": "string", "container": "string", "start_time": "string", "end_time": "string", "step": "string", "period": "string" }</pre>
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "namespace": "slice1", "deployment": "streamer-slice1-deployment", "pod": "streamer-slice1", "container": "streamer-slice1", "start_time": "2024-04-25 7:00:00", "end_time": "2024-04-25 8:00:00", "step": "1m", "period": "2m" }</pre>
Response Schema	<pre>"responses": { "200": { "description": "Query success" }, "400": { "description": "Invalid request data" } }</pre>
Response Example	The response body contains the CSV file.
Impact on #Component 1	The Metrics Collector collects the data based on the specified information in the POST request sent by EDoS Mitigator and returns the collected metrics in a CSV file.
Impact on #Component 2	The EDoS Mitigator initiates the metrics collection for a specified application and time period, and receives the requested metrics in a CSV file in the response body sent by the Metrics Collector.

EDoS Mitigator – Admission Controller

Field	Description
Interface code	EDoS_M-AC
Status	development
Component #1	EDoS Mitigator
Component #2	Admission Controller (Validating Webhook interfaced with K8s HPA)
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	This endpoint allows to Admission Controller to request EDoS Mitigator to assess if the scaling request is legitimate or malicious.
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/api/v1/validate
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	Schema of the request/data
Request/Data Example	<pre>{ "namespace": "slice1", "deployment": "streamer-slice1-deployment", "app": "streamer-slice1" }</pre>
Response Schema	<pre>"responses": { "200": { "description": "Query success" }, "400": { "description": "Invalid request data" } }</pre>
Response Example	The response body contains the decision on whether an anomaly exists or not and provides the anomaly score. <pre>{ "anomaly": false, "msg": "No anomaly detected (-0.012215535156428814)" }</pre>
Impact on #Component 1	The EDoS Mitigator first requests the Metrics Collector to collect the metrics data of the application specified in the POST request sent by Admission Controller. The metrics are then analysed by the DL model incorporated in EDoS Mitigator to assess if there is an anomaly or not. The assessment result is sent back to the Admission Controller.
Impact on #Component 2	The Admission Controller initiates the validation process of a scaling request by specifying the application triggering the scaling operation, and receives the validation results as response. In case of anomaly, the Admission Controller prevents the K8s HPA to perform the horizontal scaling.

Security Orchestrator – Intent-based Security Policy Manager

Field	Description
Interface code	SO-ISM
Status	development
Component #1	Security Orchestrator

Component #2	Intent-based Security Policy Manager
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Translate MSPL policies from the decision engine into specific configuration messages for the affected Security Agents
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	MSPL
Endpoint	:8001
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	Is dependant on the policy to enforce
Request/Data Example	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://modeliosoft/xsddesigner/a22bd60b-ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59" orchestrationID="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" > <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>fl_agent</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FederatedLearningRuleAction"> <federationLearnigActionType>AGENT</federationLearnigActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="FLConfigurationCondition"> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <instanceThreshold>100000</instanceThreshold> <aggregatorParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <URL>localhost:3333</URL> <apiPort>9090</apiPort> </aggregatorParameters> <localConnectionParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <apiPort>9999</apiPort> </localConnectionParameters> <integrationFabricParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <URL>155.54.98.125:29092</URL> </integrationFabricParameters> <topics> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <topic> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <purpose>training-flows-inffo</purpose> </topic> </topics> </configurationCondition> </configurationRule> </configuration> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>

	<pre><name>training-flows-inffo</name> </topic> </topics> </integrationFabricParameters> <learningModelInfo> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <learningType>unsupervised</learningType> <modelParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <type>neural-network</type> <subtype>autoencoder</subtype> <additionalParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <encoderLayers>2</encoderLayers> <decoderLayers>2</decoderLayers> <encoderNeurons>32-16</encoderNeurons> <decoderNeurons>16-32</decoderNeurons> <codeNeurons>8</codeNeurons> <lossFunction>mean-squared-error</lossFunction> </additionalParameters> </modelParameters> </learningModelInfo> <learningParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <testSize>0.33</testSize> <localEpochs>1</localEpochs> <batchSize>32</batchSize> <stepsPerEpoch>1</stepsPerEpoch> </learningParameters> <obfuscationInfo> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <technique>differential-privacy</technique> <parameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <mechanism>laplace-truncated</mechanism> <additionalParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <epsilon>1.0</epsilon> <delta>0.0</delta> </additionalParameters> </parameters> </obfuscationInfo> </configurationCondition> <externalData xsi:type="Priority"> <value>60000</value> </externalData></pre>
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	<pre> <Name>Rule0</Name> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> <Name>Conf0</Name> </configuration> <enablerCandidates> <enabler>agent</enabler> </enablerCandidates> <enforcementRequirements> <enforcementDomains> <domainID>IDdomain</domainID> </enforcementDomains> </enforcementRequirements> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration> </pre> <p>(Example of a Federated Learning policy)</p>
Response Schema	Is dependant on the implementation of the driver, as the response is the specific configuration generated for the correspondent driver for a certain device.
Response Example	N/A
Impact on #Component 1	The Security Orchestrator requires the generation of configuration messages from the MSPL policies received from the Decision Engine
Impact on #Component 2	The Intent-based Security Policy Manager receives MSPL policies from the Security Orchestrator and generates configuration messages for specific components based on these policies

R12 Assets – AI-driven decision making (Common format)

Field	Description
Interface code	AID-PPFLAD AID-PPFAIAD AID-HSPF
Status	design
Component #1	R12 Assets
Component #2	AID
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Interface used to report network traffic anomalies
Mode	Asynchronous
Standards/Protocols	Kafka
Format	JSON
Endpoint	TBD
Operation	Publish
Request Schema	<pre> { "type": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "objects": [{ "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", </pre>

	<pre>"created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "value": "STRING", "value_type": "STRING", "flow_id": "STRING", "source_ip": "STRING", "source_port": "STRING", "destination_ip": "STRING", "destination_port": "STRING", "flow_data": "STRING", "label": "STRING" }, { "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "model_id": "STRING", "model_name": "STRING", "learning_type": "STRING", "flow_features": "STRING", "threshold": "STRING", "binary_class_accuracy": "STRING", "multi_class_accuracy": "STRING", "comparison_metric": "STRING", "framework": "STRING", "framework_version": "STRING", "collection_tool": "STRING", "collection_tool_version": "STRING", "training_timestamp": "STRING" }, { "type": "STRING", "spec_version": "STRING", "id": "STRING", "created": "STRING", "modified": "STRING", "relationship_type": "STRING", "source_ref": "STRING", "target_ref": "STRING" }] }</pre>
Request Example	<pre>{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--cd2a2cf9-18f3-480a-aaa5-c4b59ce6910b", "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--1aa7d222-ccc9-4562-ba47-2b17bf9efd86", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.870753Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.870753Z",</pre>

	<pre> "value": "1.45", "value_type": "reconstruction_error", "flow_id": "1", "source_ip": "20.1.249.77", "source_port": "61771", "destination_ip": "192.168.0.2", "destination_port": "80", "flow_data": "[4, 0, 4, 0, 248, 248, 1672.74, 0]", "label": "anomaly" }, { "type": "model", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "model--30772ca8-067b-4f88-a45f-f5b8579c088c", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.940615Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.940615Z", "model_id": "model1", "model_name": "MLP", "learning_type": "supervised", "flow_features": "['SrcPkts', 'DstPkts', 'TotPkts', 'DstBytes', 'SrcBytes', 'TotBytes', 'SrcLoad', 'DstLoad', '...']", "threshold": "1.20", "binary_class_accuracy": "99.70", "multi_class_accuracy": "99.70", "comparison_metric": "softmax", "framework": "tensorflow", "framework_version": "v0.2.1", "collection_tool": "nfstream", "collection_tool_version": "v0.6.0", "training_timestamp": "1921290190290" }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--54732f74-09f8-416d-82f6-4e55c47a5367", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.963371Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.963371Z", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "model--30772ca8-067b-4f88-a45f-f5b8579c088c", "target_ref": "anomalies--1aa7d222-ccc9-4562-ba47-2b17bf9efd86" }] } </pre>
Response Schema	NA
Response Example	NA
Impact on #Component 1	The R12 Assets report network traffic anomalies to the AID following the specified unified data model
Impact on #Component 2	The AID receives the details of the detected network traffic anomalies from the R12 Assets

AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision – Security Orchestrator

Field	Description
Interface code	AI_RM-SO
Status	development
Component #1	AI-driven algorithm for risk management and mitigation provision
Component #2	Security Orchestrator
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Generate specific configuration messages for devices to enforce policies from the De
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	MSPL
Endpoint	:8002/meservice
Operation	POST
Request/Data Schema	Is dependent on the policy to enforce
Request/Data Example	<pre><?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?> <ITResourceOrchestration xmlns="http://modeliosoft/xsddesig beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" id="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9" xsi:schemaLocation="http://mo ee3d-425c-8618-beb6a854051a/ITResource.xsd mspl.xsd"> <ITResource id="mspl_9e9dl orchestrationID="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9"> <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration"> <capability> <Name>commandControl</Name> </capability> <configurationRule> <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="CommandControlRuleAction"> <commandControlActionType>CAMERA</commandControlActionType> </configurationRuleAction> <configurationCondition xsi:type="CommandControlConfigurationCondition"> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <cameraRuleParameters> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> <request>>true</request> <action>stoprecording</action> <macAddress>00:00:00:00:00</macAddress> <command_id>1234567890</command_id> </cameraRuleParameters> </configurationCondition> <externalData xsi:type="Priority"> <value>60000</value> </externalData> <Name>Rule0</Name> <isCNF>>false</isCNF> </configurationRule> </ITResource> </configuration> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre>

	<pre><Name>Conf0</Name> </configuration> <enablerCandidates> <enabler>one_mobitrust</enabler> </enablerCandidates> </ITResource> </ITResourceOrchestration></pre> <p>(Example of a stop recording policy from the ONE Mobitrust use case)</p>
Response Schema	Is dependant on the implementation of the driver in charge of the MSPL processing, 200 - OK.
Response Example	NA
Impact on #Component 1	The Decision Engine generates a MSPL policy to mitigate an anomaly detected in the
Impact on #Component 2	The Security Orchestrator processes the MSPL policy received and generates a config device in order to enforce the policy

Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification – Security Orchestrator

Field	Description
Interface code	SO-TESF
Status	development
Component #1	TESF
Component #2	Security Orchestrator
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Request for Trust score from the any management domain entities to the TESF for network entities(for example IMSI)
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON (STIX2)
Endpoint	Endpoint - :8000/target
Operation	GET
Request/Data Schema	{ "target_id": "IMSI" }
Request/Data Example	{ "target_id": "999700000000001" } "GET /target?value=999700000000001 HTTP/1.1"
Response Schema	{ "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--dbda0f4f-fe0c-41af-88f8-e14684d2404f", "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--9da20a70-db81-40ee-bf94-d19e0d40d785", "created": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268452+00:00", "modified": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268452+00:00",

	<pre> "error_type": "re-registration", "ip": "999700000000001", "trust_score": 80, "revoked": false }, { "type": "networkentity", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "networkentity--ea929359-d9de-43dd-a0d3-1ae66d55ca88", "created": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268794+00:00", "modified": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268794+00:00", "name": "amf", "ip": "127.0.0.5", "revoked": false }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--381ef38b-711e-4f95-801d-022a1e3e0cfa", "created": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268979+00:00", "modified": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268979+00:00", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "anomalies--9da20a70-db81-40ee-bf94-d19e0d40d785", "target_ref": "networkentity--ea929359-d9de-43dd-a0d3-1ae66d55ca88", "revoked": false }] } </pre>
Response Example	Given in Response Schema
Impact on #Component 1	The SO will get the trust score and will act based on the defined policy for taking an proactive or reactive measures.
Impact on #Component 2	The TESH will provide the trust score of the network entity.

Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework specification – AI-driven decision-making

Field	Description
Interface code	TESF-AID
Status	design
Component #1	TESF
Component #2	Decision Engine
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	The TESH will send the trust score, ip of a network entity and impacted ip to the Decision Engine in events where the trust score of a network is below a given threshold
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON (STIX2)
Endpoint	kafka topic
Operation	publish
Request/Data Schema	<pre> { "type": "bundle", "id": "bundle--dbda0f4f-fe0c-41af-88f8-e14684d2404f", </pre>

	<pre> "objects": [{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "anomalies--9da20a70-db81-40ee-bf94-d19e0d40d785", "created": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268452+00:00", "modified": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268452+00:00", "error_type": "re-registration", "ip": "999700000000001", "trust_score": 30, "revoked": false }, { "type": "networkentity", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "networkentity--ea929359-d9de-43dd-a0d3-1ae66d55ca88", "created": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268794+00:00", "modified": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268794+00:00", "name": "amf", "ip": "127.0.0.5", "revoked": false }, { "type": "relationship", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "relationship--381ef38b-711e-4f95-801d-022a1e3e0cfa", "created": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268979+00:00", "modified": "2024-05-14T11:54:04.268979+00:00", "relationship_type": "indicates", "source_ref": "anomalies--9da20a70-db81-40ee-bf94-d19e0d40d785", "target_ref": "networkentity--ea929359-d9de-43dd-a0d3-1ae66d55ca88", "revoked": false }] </pre>
Request/Data Example	Given in Request Schema
Response Schema	N.A
Response Example	N.A
Impact on #Component 1	When the trust score threshold of network entity like UE is below a certain threshold(customizable), the TESP will publish the given data to a specific kafka topic.
Impact on #Component 2	The decision engine subscribed to the same kafka topic will take some decision based on the trust score and other related features (which may result in a threat mitigation).

Holistic Security and Privacy Framework – MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)

Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#1 to #2

Description	Interface provided by the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/MTDaas
Operation	POST
Request Schema	{ "id": "NUMBER", "model_type": "NUMBER", "num_of_clients": "NUMBER", "data_provider_address": "STRING", "num_of_master_model_neurons": "NUMBER", "num_of_slave_model_neurons": "NUMBER", "num_of_iterations": "NUMBER" }
Request Example	{ "id": 10, "model_type": 0, "num_of_clients": 5, "data_provider_address": "192.168.1.196:8080", "num_of_master_model_neurons": 32, "num_of_slave_model_neurons": 28, "num_of_iterations": 3 }
Response Schema	{ "id": "NUMBER" }
Response Example	{ "id": 3 }
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF requests an MTD instance via the provided interface.
Impact on #Component 2	MTD component provides an interface so the HSPF may instantiate an MTD instance.
Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#1 to #2
Description	Interface provided by the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/MTDaas/{id}
Operation	GET
Request Schema	NA
Request Example	NA
Response Schema	{ "id": "NUMBER", "accuracy": "NUMBER", "resilience": "NUMBER" }
Response Example	{ "id": 3, "accuracy": 0.99, "resilience": 0.7 }
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF requests the KPIs from an MTD instance.

Impact on #Component 2	MTD component provides an interface so the HSPF may collect the associated KPIs.
Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Interface used to provide FLaaS for the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/flaaS/model
Operation	POST
Request Schema	<pre>{ "id": "NUMBER", "client_id": "NUMBER", "model_type": "NUMBER", "weights": "ARRAY" }</pre>
Request Example	<pre>{ "id": 1, "client_id": 5, "weights": [[[0.1, 0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.1, 0.4]], [[0.9], [0.2], [0.1]]] }</pre>
Response Schema	<pre>{ "id": "NUMBER" }</pre>
Response Example	<pre>{ "flaaS_id": "10" }</pre>
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF provides FLaaS capabilities to be consumed by the MTD mechanism.
Impact on #Component 2	The MTD mechanism consumes the FLaaS functionalities provided by the HSPF.
Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Interface used to provide FLaaS for the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/flaaS/model/{id}
Operation	GET
Request Schema	NA
Request Example	NA
Response Schema	{

	<pre>"weights": "ARRAY" }</pre>
Response Example	<pre>{ "weights": [[0.1, 0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.1, 0.4]], [[0.9], [0.2], [0.1]] }</pre>
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF provides FLaaS capabilities to be consumed by the MTD mechanism.
Impact on #Component 2	The MTD mechanism consumes the FLaaS functionalities provided by the HSPF.
Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Interface used to provide UC data for the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/data/features/{id}
Operation	GET
Request Schema	NA
Request Example	NA
Response Schema	<pre>{ "id": "NUMBER", "num_of_features": "NUMBER" }</pre>
Response Example	<pre>{ "id": 3, "num_of_features": 25 }</pre>
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF collects and provides network data from a specific UC and provides it to the MTD component.
Impact on #Component 2	The MTD receives the network data collected by the HSPF from a specific UC and uses it to train MTD models.
Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Interface used to provide UC data for the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/data/training/{id}
Operation	GET
Request Schema	NA
Request Example	NA

Response Schema	{ "id": "NUMBER", "data": "ARRAY" }
Response Example	{ "id": 3, "data": [[0.3, 0.1, 0.5, 0.4, 0.6], [0.8, 0.7, 0.2, 0.9, 0.5]] }
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF collects and provides network data from a specific UC and provides it to the MTD component.
Impact on #Component 2	The MTD receives the network data collected by the HSPF from a specific UC and uses it to train MTD models.
Field	Description
Interface code	HSPF-MTD
Status	development
Component #1	HSPF (R12)
Component #2	MTD (R14)
Direction	#2 to #1
Description	Interface used to provide UC data for the MTD component
Mode	Synchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST
Format	JSON
Endpoint	/data/testing/{id}
Operation	GET
Request Schema	NA
Request Example	NA
Response Schema	{ "id": "NUMBER", "data": "ARRAY" }
Response Example	{ "id": 3, "data": [[0.3, 0.1, 0.5, 0.4, 0.6], [0.8, 0.7, 0.2, 0.9, 0.5]] }
Impact on #Component 1	HSPF collects and provides network data from a specific UC and provides it to the MTD component.
Impact on #Component 2	The MTD receives the network data collected by the HSPF from a specific UC and uses it to train MTD models.

AI-driven decision making – Threat Risk Assessor

Field	Description
Interface code	AID-TRA-KAFKA
Status	Design Active
Component #1	AID Client
Component #2	TRA / Kafka
Direction	Inbound / Outbound
Description	Handle requests from AID Client to retrieve STIX data from TRA via Kafka topics.

Mode	Asynchronous
Standards/Protocols	REST (HTTP)
Format	JSON
Endpoint	`/API/request`
Operation	POST/GET
Request/Data Schema	`{ „bundle_ids“: [„bundle_id_1“, „bundle_id_2“] }`
`Request/Data Example	`{ "bundle_ids": ["bundle--12345678-1234-1234-1234-123456789012", "bundle--98741-4172-6219-444-98765432198"] }`
Response Schema	<pre>{ "data_details": [{ "bundle_id": "bundle--12345678-1234-1234-1234-123456789012", "data": { "anomalies": [/* array of vulnerability objects */], "model": [/* array of attack-pattern objects */], "relationship": [/* array of relationship objects */] } }], }</pre>
Response Example	<pre>{ "type": "anomalies", "spec_version": "2.1", "id": "1aa7d222-ccc9-4562-ba47-2b17bf9efd86", "created": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.870753Z", "modified": "2024-04-09T13:41:01.870753Z", "value": "1.45", "value_type": "reconstruction_error", "flow_id": "1", "source_ip": "20.1.249.77", "source_port": "61771", "destination_ip": "192.168.0.2", "destination_port": "80", "flow_data": "[4, 0, 4, 0, 248, 248, 1672.74, 0]", "label": "anomaly" }</pre>
Impact on #Component 1	Receives the STIX data & risk score based on bundle IDs from TRA.
Impact on #Component 2	TRA Dynamically retrieves Stix data from Kafka based on data types & Kafka topics as configured in the config. JSON file.

ANNEX V: INLAB TESTING – INITIAL PERIOD TESTS

Information on Tests Performed and planned to be performed per Asset								
#	Asset(s) name	Partner(s) involved	Test description	Planned or already Performed	Testbed(s) involved	Test expected results	Test actual results	Comments and references
1	Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	UMU	Binary and multi-class classification using publicly available datasets (e.g., 5G-NIDD)	Performed	UMU	Exceed accuracy and minimum detection time specified in KPIs (>95% accuracy, order of ms in detection time)	98% accuracy (no-DP) and 95% (DP with epsilon=1), ~50ms of detection time per sample	N/A
2	Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	UMU, ONE	Binary and multi-class classification using real/simulated data from the testbed	Planned	ONE	Exceed accuracy and minimum detection time specified in KPIs (>95% accuracy, order of ms in detection time)	N/A	N/A
3	Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	UMU	Check that the output of the asset complies with the agreed data models (STIXv2 format)	Planned	UMU	The output should be published without errors in the Kafka topic enabled for this purpose and should comply with the data-model template	N/A	N/A
4	ISM Slice manager configuration	UMU, UWS	Check that the connection, translation and	Performed	ORO	The connection, translation and	Worked correctly	N/A

			configuration are carried out correctly.			configuration are carried out correctly.		
5	ISM OpenC2 configuration	UMU, ONE	Check that the connection, translation and configuration are carried out correctly.	Performed	ONE	The connection, translation and configuration are carried out correctly.	Worked correctly	N/A
6	Multi-domain security slice management	UMU	Deployment of IPsec tunnels between network devices in a single-domain SDN-based environment	Performed	UMU	The component is able to create IPsec tunnels on-demand for a set of network devices	Worked correctly	N/A
7	Multi-domain security slice management	UMU	Deployment of IPsec tunnels between network devices in a multi-domain SDN-based environment	Planned	UMU	The component is able to create IPsec tunnels on-demand for a set of network devices	N/A	N/A
8	AI-driven Security Orchestrator	UMU	Allocation placement and configuration for a Security Agent (e.g., a FL agent)	Planned	UMU	A list of the enabler candidates (that are available, meet the requirements and can be deployed) should be generated, and the most suitable one should be selected for the enforcement	N/A	N/A
9	AI-driven Security Orchestrator	UMU	Enforcement configuration and deployment for a		UMU	The enabler should be deployed and configured	N/A	N/A

			Security Agent (e.g., a FL agent)			successfully in the selected candidate		
10	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator	OULU, ICTFI	EDoS Mitigator can extract metrics from Monitoring System and provide anomaly score	Already performed on OULU, Planned on ICTFI	OULOU, ICTFI	The required metrics are effectively collected and the anomaly score provided	Passed on OULOU testbed, Not yet evaluated on ICTFI testbed	ICTFI are in the process of updating the Monitoring System of their testbed to collect the metrics needed by EDoS Mitigator.
11	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator	OULU, ICTFI	Admission Controller can intercept HPA scaling request and contact EDoS Mitigator to decide the legitimacy or maliciousness of the request. If malicious, the scaling request is blocked.	Already performed on OULU, Planned on ICTFI	OULOU, ICTFI	The scaling request is blocked by the Admission Controller in case EDoS Mitigator detects an anomaly	Passed on OULOU testbed, Not yet evaluated on ICTFI testbed	
12	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator	OULU, ICTFI	Test the effectiveness of the integrated solution (i.e., all AI-powered EDoS Mitigator's components deployed and working in a closed-	Already performed on OULU, Planned on ICTFI	OULOU, ICTFI	The scaling request is blocked by the Admission Controller in case EDoS Mitigator detects an anomaly	Passed on OULOU testbed, Not yet evaluated on ICTFI testbed	At OULOU we generated malicious traffic using Hulk and Slowloris attacks. The preliminary results showed

			loop way) in preventing autoscaling requests generated by application-layer DDoS attacks.					that the solution is able to prevent all scaling requests caused by Hulk. However, the first scaling requests caused by Slowloris can go under the radar of the EDoS Mitigator.
13	MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)	OULU	Evaluating MTD-based Robust ML for global-model-as-knowledge attack scenario 1	Planned, Have started to be implemented	OULU	Improving KPI 13 and KPI 18 in comparison with FL without MTD	Not evaluated yet	
14	MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)	OULU	Evaluating MTD-based Robust ML for global-model-as-knowledge attack scenario 2	Planned, Have started to be implemented	OULU	Improving KPI 13 and KPI 18 in comparison with FL without MTD	Not evaluated yet	
15	MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)	OULU	Evaluating MTD-based Robust ML for local-model-as-knowledge attack scenario 3	Planned, Have started to be implemented	OULU	Not be effective	Not evaluated yet	The MTD strategy will be improved in WP4, to deal with local-model-as-knowledge attack scenarios

16	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	2 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 87.7% Sensitivity: 78.7% Specificity: 87.2% F1-Score: 70.07%	
17	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	2 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training + 2 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 85% Sensitivity: 97% Specificity: 84% F1-Score: 60%	Cumulative Scenarios need further use of previous data
18	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	4 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 87% Sensitivity: 86% Specificity: 91% F1-Score: 60%	
19	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	4 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training +4 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 88% Sensitivity: 79% Specificity: 87% F1-Score: 62%	Cumulative Scenarios need further use of previous data
20	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	6 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 92% Sensitivity: 54% Specificity:	

							93% F1-Score: 67%	
21	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	6 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training + 6 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 90% Sensitivity: 95% Specificity: 90% F1-Score: 66%	Cumulative Scenarios need further use of previous data
22	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	8 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 94% Sensitivity: 66% Specificity: 96% F1-Score: 50%	
23	R12: Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	ONE	8 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training + 8 Hour Network Traffic Retrieval + Model Training	Already Performed	ONE	Accuracy: 80% Sensitivity: 70% Specificity: 70% F1-Score: 50%	Accuracy: 90% Sensitivity: 87% Specificity: 90% F1-Score: 60%	Cumulative Scenarios need further use of previous data
24	Threat Risk Assessor (TRA)	EBOS & RHEA	Interface Testing	Planned	eBOS	Data communication over REST API.	Not Started	Tentative [Further details and requirements need to be clarified by the partners.]
25	AID	eBOS	STIX message creation/storage: The test will include	Planned	eBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful creation of STIX message • Successful storage 	TBA	-

			several classifiers that process data from datasets and then create STIX messages that will be stored in Kafka.			of STIX message to Kafka		
26	AID	eBOS	Read STIX message: This test will include the successful parsing of the data from Kafka by AID.	Planned	eBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Successful communication using the Consumer API of Kafka. AID will read the STIX messages created by the classifiers.	TBA	-
27	AID	eBOS	AID functionality: After parsing the STIX data from Kafka, AID will process them and create its output.	Planned	eBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Successful processing of the STIX messages• Expected output	TBA	-